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Executive summary

This document presents the final and updated technical specification for Work Package 6 (WP6) as part of the SmartCHANGE project. It builds upon the previous version, *D6.1: Initial Technical Specification*, delivered at M18 (October 2024). While maintaining the core structure and objectives of D6.1, this final version incorporates significant updates derived from new project results, feedback from the pilot study carried out in WP7, and evolving technical and regulatory requirements.

The main goal of SmartCHANGE is to develop **trustworthy AI-based tools** to assist health professionals (HCPs) and citizens in improving public health outcomes. Through a user-centred design process, the project provides:

- i) a **mobile app** for families (including children and adolescents),
- ii) a **web application** for HCPs.

The aim is to reduce the long-term risk of non-communicable diseases (NCDs)—particularly cardiovascular and metabolic—and promote personalized, effective risk-reduction strategies.

This deliverable outlines the updated technical specifications for the SmartCHANGE system, designed following a **microservices-based architecture** and a **privacy-by-design** approach. Compared to D6.1, this version introduces several key enhancements. The SmartCHANGE platform itself has been revised and updated, to better support the clients and incorporating the advancements of the technical work packages.

In essence, this updated specification ensures that SmartCHANGE is evolving into a robust, scalable, and secure ecosystem, capable of supporting real-world deployment with **user trust, data privacy, and transparency** at its core.

List of abbreviations

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Definition</i>
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CDA	Clinical Document Architecture
CIA	Confidentiality Integrity Availability
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CVD	CardioVascular Disease
DB	Database
DBMS	Database Management System
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EMR	Electronic Medical Record
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FE	Front end
FL	Federated Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
HCP	Health Care Professional
HL7	Health Level 7

HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
IP	Internet Protocol
IPv	Internet Protocol version
IT	Information Technology
JDBC	Java Database Connectivity
JWT	JSON Web Token
MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
ML	Machine Learning
NaN	Not a Number
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OAuth	Open Authorization
OIDC	OpenID Connect
PU	Pilot User
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SCORE2	Systematic COronary Risk Evaluation 2
SDK	Software Development Kit
SSD	Solid State Drive
SSH	Secure SHell
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer

SSO	Single Sign-On
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modeling Language
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VE	Visual Explainer
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
XCDS	eXplainable Decision Support

1 Introduction

This document delivers the final and evolved technical specification deliverable for Work Package 6 (WP6) of the SmartCHANGE project. It represents a substantial update to the earlier version (*D6.1: Initial Technical Specification*, submitted at M18 – October 2024), reflecting progress made across the project, including the integration of new results, insights from the pilot study, and adaptations to emerging technical and regulatory requirements. While the overall structure and chapter organization remain consistent with D6.1, this version introduces significant refinements and additions to both the system components and the underlying design approach.

To contextualize the updates introduced, it is important to recall that the SmartCHANGE project is a pioneering initiative that leverages artificial intelligence (AI) to empower healthcare professionals (HCPs) and citizens in managing health proactively and reducing the long-term risk of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), particularly cardiovascular and metabolic conditions. Through a user-centred design process, the project provides two complementary tools:

- A **web-based application for HCPs** that offers insights and AI-driven decision support, tailored to clinical workflows.
- A **mobile application** targeted at children, adolescents, and families, integrating wearable data and lifestyle tracking to deliver personalized guidance.

In particular, key enhancements in this final specification include:

- The introduction of a comprehensive **Trustworthy AI Framework**, which replaces the previous individual Explainer and Federated Learning (FL) components.
- The introduction of a backend for the HappyPlant app and a dedicated repository for the raw Garmin data.
- The introduction of a Data Anonymizer service, to make the clinical data collected during the pilot studies accessible by project partners in an anonymised form, preserving the privacy of the participants in the studies.
- The data model has been refined and updated, and the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) mapping finalized.

- A more structured integration of **Visual Explainer**, that now interacts securely with the trustworthy AI service.

Additionally, this version introduces a more **precautionary and comprehensive approach to security and privacy**, as detailed in Chapter 3. Based on the latest findings and in alignment with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance (as previously described in D2.3 and D2.4), the document outlines updated technical and organizational safeguards, especially in the context of federated learning.

The document also continues to define:

- The specific **microservices and APIs** of the system.
- The **communication protocols** for inter-service operations.
- The **data flows**, from collection to storage, aligned the usage scenarios defined in WP3 and aligned with the new functionalities.

Overall, this deliverable presents the SmartCHANGE solution as a cohesive, privacy-aware, and scalable AI system built on a microservices architecture. It defines the system's core functionalities, internal interactions, and data handling procedures, ensuring that all services operate in line with user needs and privacy-by-design principles.

To ensure the correct implementation, integration, and deployment of the SmartCHANGE system, a comprehensive set of system requirements and constraints has been analysed. These encompass user needs, infrastructure and integration constraints, design aspects, AI functionalities, and legal and ethical considerations. The requirements have been documented across several dedicated deliverables, developed throughout the project.

The following table provides an overview of the key deliverables that inform the technical specification of the SmartCHANGE system:

Together, these deliverables provide the necessary inputs to define a technically robust, user-centred, and legally compliant SmartCHANGE system architecture.

Table 1 - inputs to the technical specification

Category	Deliverable	Description
User Requirements	D3.6 – <i>User Requirements for the mobile and web application</i>	Captures functional and non-functional requirements from the end-user perspective.
UX Design	D3.8 – <i>Updated UX design and prototypes of the mobile and web application</i>	Provides updated wireframes and interactive prototypes supporting user-centred design.
Infrastructure & Integration	D6.7 – <i>Final integration and test plan</i>	Defines infrastructure requirements and outlines integration and testing procedures for system components.
Prediction Pipeline	D4.3 – <i>Final prediction pipeline</i>	Describes the final design of the prediction pipeline, including data pre-processing and federated learning.
Trustworthy AI Suite	D5.3 – <i>Final trustworthy AI suite</i>	Provides tools and methods to enhance the explainability, robustness, and trustworthiness of AI components.
Security, Ethics and Privacy	D2.5 – <i>Midterm SELP monitoring report</i>	Reports on midterm SELP monitoring and updates on security, ethical, and legal compliance.

As anticipated, the structure of the document follows the same organization as D6.1, which was originally designed to provide a logical and layered progression, moving from system-level context and requirements to architecture, data flows, and deployment. This organization supports a clear understanding of how the SmartCHANGE solution is conceptualized, designed, secured, and implemented, while ensuring traceability with the overall project goals and user requirements. Specifically:

- **Chapter 2 – System Overview:** A high-level view of the system’s components and their roles.
- **Chapter 3 – Security and Privacy:** Enhanced content covering risk management and safeguards in the federated and AI-enabled environment.

- **Chapter 4 – Architecture Design:** A detailed breakdown of the overall system architecture, including service definitions and interactions.
- **Chapter 5 – Data Model:** Clarification of the types of data exchanged, and their secure processing across components.
- **Chapter 6 – Data Flows:** Clarification of the types of data exchanged, and their secure processing across components.
- **Chapter 7 – Deployment and Testing:** Updated methods for deploying, testing, and validating the system in real-world scenarios.
- **Chapter 8 – Conclusions and Next Steps:** A summary of key updates and directions for future technical development.

2 System Overview

2.1 Inputs to the technical specifications

For the components of the SmartCHANGE system to be correctly implemented, integrated, and deployed, multiple sets of system requirements must be considered, from the deliverables listed in Table 1.

2.1.1 User Requirements

Deliverable D3.6 provides a high-level usage scenario for the SmartCHANGE solution and lists the high-level requirements for the two main user groups:

- Healthcare Professionals (HCPs) using the web application.
- Families and Adolescents using the mobile application.

The usage scenario was derived through a co-design process involving direct input from stakeholders across all four pilot sites. It defines two primary engagement pathways within the system, which accommodate the needs of the different sites:

- School-Initiated Path – where families and adolescents are onboarded through school communities.
- HCP-Initiated Pathway – where participation is prompted by healthcare providers, such as paediatricians.

In the school-initiated pathway, users retain the option to involve a healthcare provider. Both the mobile and web applications have been designed to support these usage paths.

2.1.2 Infrastructure and Integration Requirements

Deliverable D6.7 elaborates on the infrastructure and integration aspects of the SmartCHANGE solution, including:

- Deployment strategy within a secure, scalable environment.
- Technical constraints and platform dependencies.
- Integration scenarios, describing the interactions needed between individual services and clients to fulfil a functionality.

This document sets the groundwork for the architecture and informs decisions regarding service orchestration and infrastructure readiness.

2.1.3 User eXperience Design

Deliverable D3.8, describing the UX design in SmartCHANGE plays a pivotal role in shaping the technical specification, particularly by defining the core functionalities that the two client applications—the HappyPlant mobile app and the HCP Webapp—must provide. It outlines user flows, interface behaviours, and interaction requirements specific to each client type, ensuring that both end-user and healthcare professional needs are addressed. These UX-driven specifications directly guide the development of backend services, informing the design of APIs, data handling logic, and system behaviours required to support the expected functionalities. By doing so, the UX design ensures that the backend architecture is purposefully aligned with real user interactions, enabling a coherent and user-centred system across both platforms.

2.1.4 Transition to Technical Specification

This technical specification document further refines the inputs of the previous deliverables, translating the interactions into concrete technical flows. It does so by:

- Detailing exact communication patterns between components;
- Specifying APIs and interfaces used in the implementation;
- Modelling interactions using UML sequence diagrams to ensure clarity and alignment with design goals;
- Describing the Integration with external systems;
- Analysing data protection and privacy requirements and transforming them into concrete security measures to be implemented.

2.2 System Context

The SmartCHANGE system is designed as a trustworthy AI-based decision-support solution that, as described in Figure 1, operates in a complex environment involving healthcare providers, youths as well as children and their families. It involves the use of different data sources, facilitating bidirectional communication between health professionals and citizens. The core internal components include the eXplainable Clinical Decision Support (XCDS) Engine, a Clinical Repository based on FHIR, a Trustworthy AI Frameworks that includes a Risk Prediction service, an Explainer service and services supporting Federated Learning (FL Client, and FL Server). The Security Framework ensures data integrity, privacy, and compliance with regulations. This includes user authentication via the Identity Provider, monitoring of system activities, and comprehensive logging and auditing to safeguard data transactions. All these elements work together to collect, process, analyse, and secure data.

Figure 1 – Final Logical Architecture Diagram of the SmartCHANGE solution

Externally, the solution interacts with human actors and receives inputs from wearable devices and public health datasets. The respective roles of each of these entities within the system are as follows:

- **Health Professionals (HCP):** Use the HCP Web App to access risk assessments, receive recommendations, and input user data. They interact with the system to monitor subjects, understand AI-generated insights, and make informed decisions based on personalized recommendations.
- **Children, Youth, and Families:** Engage with the system via the Youth/Family Mobile App. This tool allows users to provide data (e.g., health metrics from wearables), receive feedback on risk levels, and obtain personalized health advice.
- **Wearable Devices:** Serve as external data sources, capturing health-related information such as activity levels, heart rate, and other vital metrics. Data from these devices are processed by the system and contribute to compute individual risk profiles.
- **External Datasets:** Used by the central Trustworthy AI Framework for training and enhancing the AI models. These datasets provide additional context and benchmarks for improving predictive accuracy. Datasets owned by a specific pilot contribute to the global model training through federated learning mechanisms.

Data flows in the system according to the main flows listed below:

1. **Data Collection:** Data is collected from the HappyPlant App (directly or through wearable devices) and from the HCP Web App when professionals record data during consultations. Collected data includes personal health information, which is sent to the Clinical Repository, to make it available to the authorized services in the platform.
2. **Risk Assessment:** The HCP requests a risk prediction through the Webapp, or the HappyPlant app uses. Processed data flows to the Local Trustworthy AI Framework, using the XCDS Engine as a broker. The Explainer service orchestrates the collection of the data from the Risk Predictor and provides explanations to support the prediction.
3. **Goal Setting:** The HCP consults the dashboard of the child or adolescents to assess their status. Using this information, they set goals to improve behaviour and potentially reduce the risk of developing diseases in the future.
4. **Federated Learning:** Local data contributes to federated learning processes, allowing the FL Client to train models without sharing raw data externally. The FL Server aggregates these updates, enhancing the system's predictive capabilities.

These flows have been further analysed and specialized in D6.3¹, as integration scenarios. Textual descriptions in D6.7² have been translated in formal sequence diagrams, and each detailed in section 6. The solution is based on the microservice architectural paradigm. In this context, a microservice is a distinct, independently deployable unit of software that focuses on performing a single, specific business function, typically communicating with other microservices through lightweight protocols like HTTP or messaging queues [64]. The system is designed to operate in a cloud-based and distributed environment, allowing scalability, flexibility, and the ability to integrate with multiple pilots and datasets. It supports real-time data processing and secure model training across distributed locations.

2.3 Key Components and Their Roles

This section gives a high-level description of the components of the SmartCHANGE solution and their role, whereas a more in-depth description will be provided in section 4.2

- **HappyPlant mobile application:** client for children and families, available as a mobile app for smartphones.

¹ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D6.3 – Initial SmartCHANGE solution prototype

² SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D6.7 – Final integration and test plan

- **HCP Webapp:** client for healthcare professionals, teachers and administrators, available as a web app running in the users' browser.
- **A FHIR-based Clinical Repository:** Central to the system, the repository is the central storage for clinical data across the SmartCHANGE solution. Both the HCP Web App and the HappyPlant App read from and write to this repository. The clinical data present in the repository is also the basis for risk predictions from the Trustworthy AI Framework.
- **XCDS (eXplainable Clinical Decision Support) Engine:** this service receives request from clients and preprocesses responses from the Trustworthy AI Framework, to make them available to the HCP Web App and the HappyPlant App. It has the responsibility to retrieve the information needed to the AI services from the FHIR Repository, where health data is securely stored and managed.
- **Trustworthy AI Framework:** The framework includes all the services that enable training of the AI models, following a Federated Learning architecture, and that provide the AI predictions. The central framework coordinates FL across multiple pilots, aggregating knowledge from various FL Clients. It communicates with a centralized FL Server that hosts a model repository and integrates public datasets for model improvement. The local framework includes several sub-components:
 - **Risk Predictor:** Utilizes health data to predict individual risk levels.
 - **Explainer:** Provides interpretable insights into AI-generated risk predictions.
 - **FL Client:** A FL component that enables collaborative model training using local data without sharing raw data.
- **Security Framework:** To ensure the system's trustworthiness and appropriate security measures, services providing identity management, monitoring, logging, and auditing are available for the whole solution.
- **Data Cleaning:** Existing datasets are cleaned and pre-processed before being used to train the Risk Prediction Models, ensuring high-quality input for reliable risk assessment.
- **Data Anonymization:** Service that transforms clinical data collected during the use of SmartCHANGE platform into datasets suitable for research. Such datasets can be anonymized or not.

This microservice-based architecture facilitates secure, bi-directional communication among the components, ensuring that both HCPs and citizens receive accurate, personalized, and actionable risk assessments. The overall system supports a scalable, FL approach, enabling the integration of diverse data sources while maintaining data privacy.

3 Security and Privacy Considerations

This section describes how the SmartCHANGE solution protects its data, users and resources, following the constraints posed by the GDPR regulations and a privacy-by-design approach. A specific focus has been placed on the Security and Privacy implications of adopting a Federated Learning approach. This chapter then reports the results of the risk assessment performed according to the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) guidelines [14], and the corresponding security measures that have been adopted in designing, developing and maintaining the SmartCHANGE solution, applying the recommendation provided in D2.5³, section 4.3.

In line with a conservative and forward-looking regulatory approach, this new version of the document addresses regulatory considerations in section 3.3 .

3.1 Security in a Federated Learning Architecture

In the context of Federated Learning (FL), **security** refers to the protection of the FL process from malicious attacks, erroneous inputs, and other threats that could compromise the integrity, and availability of the data, models, and communication channels involved. Conversely, **privacy** is concerned with protecting the confidentiality of the participants' data throughout the FL process, ensuring that sensitive information remains secure and is not exposed to other participants or external entities.

3.1.1 Security Risks and Countermeasures in SmartCHANGE

The SmartCHANGE project operates within a cross-silo FL framework, where trusted institutions collaborate to train a machine learning model without directly sharing their sensitive data. Given that all participating institutions are validated, bounded by legal contracts (e.g., Data Transfer Agreements and the Consortium Contract) and motivated to contribute effectively to the training process, and no external entities are permitted to participate in the process (i.e., the FL framework is accessible only to the consortium members), the inherent security risks that could degrade the final model's performance are

³ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D2.5 Final SELP monitoring report

significantly reduced (Figure 2). Moreover, robust server-side aggregation methods can be implemented to detect and exclude suspicious updates from unverified sources, further enhancing security [17][18][19][20]. These countermeasures are designed to operate entirely on the server side, without necessitating modifications to the underlying FL system architecture.

3.1.2 Privacy Risks and Countermeasures in SmartCHANGE

While FL inherently enhances privacy by not directly sharing sensitive data across institutions, recent studies have revealed that trained machine learning models can inadvertently leak sensitive information about the data on which they were trained, particularly under conditions such as model overfitting, reduced batch sizes, and other specific scenarios [21][22][23][24]. The potential attack vectors in a FL system —i.e., the points through which an adversary can gain unauthorised access to sensitive information—include the communication channels, client entities (i.e., institutions), and the server.

To mitigate these risks, the SmartCHANGE project implements several key countermeasures. Firstly, RPC, a widely used communication framework in distributed systems, is employed [25]. This framework uses SSL/TLS protocols to secure data transmission between clients and the server, ensuring that all communication is encrypted and authenticated, thus protecting against eavesdropping and unauthorized access.

Secondly, the SmartCHANGE FL system requires rigorous institution or user verification for participation in the training phase or when submitting queries during the inference phase in real-world deployment (Figure 2). This verification process distinguishes our system from public AI-based services, allowing only verified SmartCHANGE entities — such as consortium members, medical professionals, or citizens — to interact with the model. Entities unable to provide SmartCHANGE verification are denied access to both contributing data to the training process and querying the system for predictions.

Furthermore, the project considers the integration of advanced privacy-preserving techniques, including Differential Privacy [26][27][28][29], Secure Multiparty Computation [30][31], or Homomorphic Encryption [32][33][34]. While these techniques may involve trade-offs, such as reduced model accuracy or increased computational demands, they offer additional privacy protections without requiring fundamental changes to the FL framework and can be implemented with minimal adjustments on the client or server side. In particular, Differential Privacy can provide formal privacy guarantees by ensuring that the inclusion or exclusion of any single data point has a limited impact on the overall model, thereby protecting individual data from inference attacks.

Figure 2 - Overview of the SmartCHANGE system during the training and inference phases. Unlike in cross-client FL, In the training phase involves, only verified SmartCHANGE institutions participate in the model training. Unlike public AI-based services, while in the inference phase, restricts the final model access only responds to queries from verified clients only. This approach enhances security compared to cross-client federated learning and public AI-based services.

3.2 Risk Assessment

Risk assessment is a systematic process of identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing potential risks that could adversely affect an organization, project, or system, considering the specific operational context. Within the cybersecurity context, the process generally includes the following steps [35][36]:

- 1

RISK

Identification of Risks: Recognizing and listing all possible threats and vulnerabilities associated with data processing activities, including unauthorized access, data breaches, loss, or misuse of personal information.
- 2

Evaluation of Risks: Analysing the likelihood and potential impact of each identified risk considering factors such as the nature of the data, processing activities, and existing security measures.
- 3

Prioritization of Risks: Ranking the risks based on their assessed impact and probability to determine which ones require immediate attention or mitigation.

Mitigation Strategies: Developing strategies and actions to reduce or eliminate the identified risks, thereby minimizing their potential impact, such as enhancing security controls, establishing data protection policies, and ensuring compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.

Monitoring and Review: Continuously monitoring the effectiveness of risk mitigation measures and regularly reviewing and updating the risk assessment to address new threats and changes in the operational environment.

In the context of the **SmartCHANGE solution**, the process outlined above has been developed through three key phases:

- **Data Analysis:** Determining the level of sensitivity of the clinical and personal data being processed (details in sub-section 3.2.1).
- **Impact Analysis:** Assessing the potential harm to individuals and the organization if risks materialize (see details in sub-section 3.2.2).
- **Security measures:** Establishing measures such as encryption, access controls, and regular security audits to protect data integrity and confidentiality (details in section 3.4).

3.2.1 Data Analysis

The data integrated into the **SmartCHANGE solution** have been identified through the platform's use requirements and co-creation sessions, as detailed in deliverables D3.6⁴ and D4.1⁵ and reported in section 2.1 and section 5.1 of this document. Due to the nature of this data, which also includes sensitive personal information from adolescents and children, the related analysis indicated a high level of risk. This activity ensured that the appropriate security measures were implemented throughout the process to protect the data, as further discussed in the Impact Analysis section (3.2.2).

⁴ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D3.6 User requirements for the mobile and web application

⁵ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D4.1 Datasets and framework of health determinants

In addition, following the **privacy-by-design** principles outlined in D2.3⁶ and D2.4⁷, SmartCHANGE aims to minimize risks of not being compliant to GDPR regulations. Clinical sensitive data, when personal (i.e. not anonymous) clearly fall under the scope of the GDPR. SmartCHANGE, therefore, adheres to core principles such as lawfulness, data minimization, and confidentiality to safeguard data subjects' rights.

3.2.2 Impact Analysis

The potential impacts on subjects, whose data would be processed in the **SmartCHANGE solution**, were assessed in D2.4, while the related outcomes are reported below in relation to the CIA (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability) concepts (also known as CIA triad), as illustrated in Figure 3 [45][46].

Figure 3 - CIA triad

The assessment results are categorized into three possible outcomes - low, medium, and high impact levels - based on the severity of potential consequences. A *low impact* indicates minimal data disruption with limited effects, a *medium impact* reflects noticeable but manageable consequences on data, and a *high impact* suggests severe, long-term damage to data confidentiality, integrity, or availability.[61][62]

⁶ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D2.3 SELP Compliance Framework

⁷ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D2.4 SELP Impact Assessment

To determine these impact levels for the SmartCHANGE solution, a detailed analysis was conducted that connects the inherent nature of the data with the security architecture described throughout this document. The reasoning acknowledges that the high sensitivity of the data being processed - including clinical and personal information from adolescents and children, as mentioned in the Data Analysis (section 3.2.1) - inherently elevates the potential impact of any security incident.

Consequently, the **potential impact on confidentiality, integrity, and availability has been estimated as “high”**. This high-impact rating serves as a conservative baseline, underscoring the necessity for the robust security controls, which include both the architectural principles outlined in section 3.1 and the specific technical measures detailed in section 3.4 . While these combined measures are designed to significantly reduce the probability of an incident, the potential harm, should an incident occur, remains high.

These impact levels provide a framework for understanding the potential risks associated with data processing, particularly concerning the CIA concepts, which are critical for evaluating the security and privacy implications of the SmartCHANGE solution, as detailed below.

- **Confidentiality** means protecting information from unauthorized access. The **loss of confidentiality of personal and sensitive data** could have a significant impact on the subjects’ rights and freedoms. In particular, the following factors were considered:
 - the **main impacts on those concerned if the risk materialized**: loss of dignity, identity theft, loss of control over their data, loss of trust, psychological damage, loss of reputation.
 - the **main threats that could materialize the risk**: illicit dissemination of personal data, illegal access to computer systems, interception of data on the web portal.
 - the **sources of risk**: internal human sources, external human sources, natural sources.
 - the **measures identified that help to mitigate the risk**: encryption, traceability, logical access control, vulnerability control, physical access control, security of computer channels, personnel management, hardware security, sign a contract with the data controller, fight against malware.

Based on the confidentiality factors analysed, the **level of impact on loss of confidentiality was estimated as high**.

- **Integrity** means ensuring data are trustworthy, complete, and unaltered. The **loss of integrity** could compromise the accuracy, consistency and reliability of the data processed within the SmartCHANGE solution. The following factors were considered to define the level of impact:
 - the **main impacts on those concerned if the risk materialized**: if data is altered, either intentionally or accidentally, it could lead to incorrect assessments, decisions, or

actions based on false information, loss of control over the data, psychological damage.

- the **main threats that could have materialized the risk**: illegal access to computer systems, interception of data on the web portal and app, unlawful dissemination of personal data.
- the **sources of risk**: internal human sources, external human sources, natural sources.
- the **measures identified that help to mitigate the risk**: backup, data minimization, fight against malware, hardware security, control of physical access.

Based on the integrity factors analysed, the **level of impact on loss of integrity was estimated as high**.

- **Availability** means making data accessible when needed.

The **loss of availability** refers to the inability to use the data when needed. This risk is closely related to the **loss of integrity** and for this reason, the same considerations were applied in estimating the level of impact of loss of availability risk. Thus, the **level of impact on loss of availability was estimated as high**.

The results of this initial assessment of the **risk impact level** were used as input for the subsequent analysis phase, focusing on the **probability of threat occurrences** in the **SmartCHANGE solution**. In particular, this analysis included the **identification of main threats, risk sources**, and the corresponding **mitigation measures**.

Based on this analysis, the **probability of each threat occurring is therefore estimated as low**, not due to a low potential impact (which remains high), but rather to the effectiveness of the mitigation measures described in section 3.4 , which address each component of the CIA triad:

- **Confidentiality**

The **probability** for a breach of data confidentiality is estimated as **low** due to a multi-layered defence. This includes the inherent privacy-preserving nature of the Federated Learning architecture (section 3.1), granular access controls and strong authentication mechanisms (see Access control and authentication), encryption of data, and pseudonymization techniques (see Server/Database security) to protect against unauthorized access.

- **Integrity**

The **probability** for data integrity to be compromised or altered is estimated as **low**. This is primarily ensured by immutable logging and monitoring systems (see Logging and monitoring) that create an audit trail of all data interactions, combined with the same strict access controls (see Access control and authentication) that prevent unauthorized modifications.

- **Availability**

The **probability of the risk of data loss** was estimated to be **low** in view of planned security measures and in particular backup procedures (Back-ups).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Based on the outcomes of the previous impact analysis, it was possible to produce the **Impact Analysis Matrix** (Table 2) that reports the values of (i) risk impact levels and (ii) likelihood of threat occurrences.

Table 2 - Impact Analysis Matrix

		Risk Impact Level		
		LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Probability Of Threat Occurrences	LOW			X
	MEDIUM			
	HIGH			

In particular, the *Risk Impact Level* was determined as HIGH due to significant potential impacts on confidentiality, integrity, and availability, considering the *consequences of risk materialization*, the *relevant threats* and *risk sources*. Conversely, the *Probability of Threat Occurrences* was assessed as LOW, based on factors such as *relevant threats*, *risk sources*, and the *effectiveness of mitigation security measures*.

Therefore, while the **Impact Analysis Matrix** indicates a high-risk impact level, the probability of threat occurrences is expected to remain low, provided that the appropriate security measures detailed in Section 3.4 are implemented to mitigate/prevent the risks identified in the previous analysis.

3.3 Regulatory considerations

An analysis of the evolving regulatory landscape for AI in healthcare—specifically the interplay between the Medical Device Regulation (MDR 2017/745) and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) as discussed in guidance like MDCG 2025-6 [40] —prompts a forward-looking risk assessment for the SmartCHANGE solution. Given that the system’s **risk prediction module** is designed to provide functionalities supporting clinical decisions, it is prudent to consider the possibility that it could be classified as a Medical Device (MD) and, subsequently, as a **high-risk AI system** under Article 6(1) of the AIA [39].

While the official regulatory classification of the solution is subject to ongoing consortium evaluation (with a final determination expected after the completion of the feasibility study and to be reported in deliverable D2.6⁸, M48), the partners at the moment wish to carry out the feasibility study considering the mobile app a wellness application rather than a medical device *strictu sensu* reserving the medical device category for the sole risk-prediction module in relation to its use by HCPs. To ensure robust compliance during this evaluation phase, this document adopts a **precautionary approach**. This precautionary strategy, which was formulated to anticipate potential regulatory requirements, is fully aligned with the final analysis in deliverable D2.5⁹, which also supports a split classification (wellness app and potential medical device) pending feedback from the feasibility study. To ensure a comprehensive security and privacy framework, the solution's implications are analysed *as if* the overall platform—i.e., the mobile app (Happy Plant), web application, and the risk prediction component—were an integrated high-risk AI medical device. This proactive stance ensures that the project's design anticipates the most stringent potential compliance obligations.

This analytical lens requires an extension of the risk assessment activities. The technical and organizational measures described in Sections 3.2 and 3.4 are therefore interpreted to address the broader landscape introduced by the AIA, with specific attention to requirements for lifecycle risk management, data governance, human oversight, and cybersecurity for high-risk AI systems.

Under this *precautionary perspective*, the mapping between ENISA cybersecurity recommendations and the MDCG 2019-16 guidance (see Table 3) remains valid and essential. The domains of Governance, Protection, Defence, and Resilience are critical for demonstrating potential conformity with both the MDR Annex I requirements and the corresponding cybersecurity obligations in Article 15 of the AIA.

⁸ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D2.5 Final SELP monitoring report

⁹ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D2.6 Compliance monitoring report

3.4 Security Measures

This section outlines the security measures for the protection of personal data, based on the previous analysis. These measures are organized according to the two macro-categories defined by ENISA, organizational and technical, which are further divided into specific subcategories i) Access control and authentication; ii) Logging and monitoring; iii) Server/Database security; iv) Workstation security; v) Network/Communication security; vi) Backups; vii) Mobile/Portable devices; viii) Application lifecycle security; ix) Data deletion/disposal; x) Physical security, following the specifications described in ISO/IEC 27001 Annex A and ISO/IEC 27002. In this specific context, *the focus is on the technical ones*. [15]

However, it is important to note that these measures contribute to GDPR compliance; nevertheless, certain measures - particularly those pertaining to the underlying infrastructure, *such as server and database, mobile and portable devices, workstation and physical security, backups* - are delegated to the infrastructure provider and are not implemented directly within the solution itself. Under each subcategory, measures are assigned:

1. a **unique identifier** in the format: <SECTION_LETTER>.<NUMBER>, where
 - the SECTION_LETTER indicates the category to which the measure belongs.
 - the NUMBER represents the specific position of the measure in that category.Both tags (i.e., SECTION_LETTER and NUMBER) follow an alphabetical and numerical order.
2. a **risk assessment level** - low (L), medium (M), high (H) - based on its potential impact according to the CIA triad, as described in the previous section.

ACCESS CONTROL AND AUTHENTICATION

The security measures for access control and authentication are implemented through mechanisms that restrict access to personal data, ensuring that only authorized users can access the system. The system identifies users with administrative roles who are responsible for creating and deleting accounts, while the approval/review process takes place externally to the medical records system. Generic accounts are not supported by the application, so each user has a personal account. Authentication is based on personal usernames and passwords, with password security levels being configurable.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	K.1	An access control system applicable to all users accessing the IT system should be implemented. The system should allow creating, approving, reviewing and deleting user accounts.
L	K.2	The use of common user accounts should be avoided. In cases where this is necessary, it should be ensured that all users of the common account have the same roles and responsibilities.
L	K.3	An authentication mechanism should be in place, allowing access to the IT system (based on the access control policy and system). As a minimum a username/password combination should be used. Passwords should respect a certain (configurable) level of complexity.
L	K.4	The access control system should have the ability to detect and not allow the usage of passwords that don't respect a certain (configurable) level of complexity.
M	K.5	A specific password policy should be defined and documented. The policy should include at least password length, complexity, validity period, as well as number of acceptable unsuccessful login attempts.
M	K.6	User passwords must be stored in a "hashed" form.
H	K.7	Two-factor authentication should preferably be used for accessing systems that process personal data. The authentication factors could be passwords, security tokens, USB sticks with a secret token, biometrics etc.
H	K.8	Device authentication should be used to guarantee that the processing of personal data is performed only through specific resources in the network.

K.7 measure is a critical control for ensuring data confidentiality and integrity as required by both GDPR and MDR Annex I, in this version of the document this measure has been implemented through Keycloak service by OIDC (see details in section 3.5).

LOGGING AND MONITORING

The use of log files is an essential security measure that is implemented by the SmartCHANGE solution to enable tracking and monitoring, particularly the access to data and hosting systems. Every data access is monitored by creating specific application logs that include a timestamp, user information, and descriptors of the access (e.g., type of operation, type of

data). These application logs are stored in a dedicated database, whose security are ensured by using technology that guarantees their integrity.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	L.1	Log files should be activated for each system/application used for the processing of personal data. They should include all types of access to data (view, modification, deletion).
L	L.2	Log files should be timestamped and adequately protected against tampering and unauthorized access. Clocks should be synchronised to a single reference time source
M	L.3	Actions of the system administrators and system operators, including addition/deletion/change of user rights should be logged.
M	L.4	There should be no possibility of deletion or modification of log files content. Access to the log files should also be logged in addition to monitoring for detecting unusual activity.
M	L.5	A monitoring system should process the log files and produce reports on the status of the system and notify for potential alerts.

SERVER/DATABASE SECURITY

Security measures related to servers and applications are integrated into the system design using a pseudonymization and data encryption.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	M.1	Database and applications servers should be configured to run using a separate account, with minimum OS privileges to function correctly.
L	M.2	Database and applications servers should only process the personal data that are actually needed to process in order to achieve its processing purposes.
M	M.3	Encryption solutions should be considered on specific files or records through software or hardware implementation.
M	M.4	Encrypting storage drives should be considered.

M	M.5	Pseudonymization techniques should be applied through separation of data from direct identifiers to avoid linking to data subject without additional information
M	M.6	Techniques supporting privacy at the database level, such as authorized queries, privacy preserving database querying, searchable encryption, etc., should be considered.

WORKSTATION SECURITY

Security for devices is governed by the internal procedures of the organizations involved in data processing. Additional rules and policies for managing workstations used for data processing are also subject to the internal procedures of each organization.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	N.1	Users should not be able to deactivate or bypass security settings.
L	N.2	Anti-virus applications and detection signatures should be configured on a weekly basis.
L	N.3	Users should not have privileges to install or deactivate unauthorized software applications.
L	N.4	The system should have session timeouts when the user has not been active for a certain time period.
L	N.5	Critical security updates released by the operating system developer should be installed regularly.
M	N.6	Anti-virus applications and detection signatures should be configured on a daily basis.
H	N.7	It should not be allowed to transfer personal data from workstations to external storage devices (e.g. USB, DVD, external hard drives).
H	N.8	Workstations used for the processing of personal data should preferably not be connected to the Internet unless security measures are in place to prevent unauthorised processing, copying and transfer of personal data on store.
H	N.9	Full disk encryption should be enabled on the workstation operating system drives.

NETWORK/COMMUNICATION SECURITY

Network security measures were implemented during the deployment phase of the solution, ensuring that all incoming connections use secure protocols and valid TLS certificates. Additionally, it has been planned to deploy firewalls in the environments hosting the solution and, optionally, intrusion detection solutions in environments exposed via public networks.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	O.1	Whenever access is performed through the Internet, communication should be encrypted through cryptographic protocols (TLS/SSL).
M	O.2	Wireless access to the IT system should be allowed only for specific users and processes. It should be protected by encryption mechanisms.
M	O.4	Traffic to and from the IT system should be monitored and controlled through Firewalls and Intrusion Detection Systems.
H	O.6	The network of the information system should be segregated from the other networks of the data controller.
H	O.7	Access to the IT system should be performed only by pre-authorized devices and terminal using techniques such as MAC filtering or Network Access Control (NAC).

BACK-UPS

Backup procedures are designed to ensure business continuity in case of data loss or damage to the software systems that store them. The availability of up-to-date backups allows this data to be restored.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	P.1	Backup and data restore procedures should be defined, documented and clearly linked to roles and responsibilities.
L	P.2	Backups should be given an appropriate level of physical and environmental protection consistent with the standards applied on the originating data.
L	P.3	Execution of backups should be monitored to ensure completeness.
L	P.4	Full backups should be carried out regularly.
H	P.9	Copies of backups should be encrypted and securely stored offline as well.

MOBILE/PORTABLE DEVICES

Security for mobile/portable devices and wearables are governed by the internal procedures of the organizations involved in data processing.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	Q.1	Mobile and portable device management procedures should be defined and documented establishing clear rules for their proper use.
L	Q.2	Mobile devices that are allowed to access the information system should be pre-registered and preauthorized.

APPLICATION LIFECYCLE SECURITY

During the design of the solution, well-known protocols and technological frameworks (e.g., OIDC protocols and Spring Security) were employed to ensure a secure development environment. Practices such as secure coding, code review, testing, and access control were considered during the code development phases. The databases were configured to ensure that personal data always remains encrypted.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	R.1	During the development lifecycle best practices, state of the art and well acknowledged secure development practices, frameworks or standards should be followed.
L	R.2	Specific security requirements should be defined during the early stages of the development lifecycle.
L	R.3	Specific technologies and techniques designed for supporting privacy and data protection (also referred to as Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs)) should be adopted in analogy to the security requirements.
L	R.4	Secure coding standards and practices should be followed.
L	R.5	During the development, testing and validation against the implementation of the initial security requirements should be performed.
M	R.6	Vulnerability assessment, application and infrastructure penetration testing should be performed by a trusted third party prior to the operational adoption. The application shall not be adopted unless the required level of security is achieved.

M	R.8	Information about technical vulnerabilities of information systems being used should be obtained.
M	R.9	Software patches should be tested and evaluated before they are installed in an operational environment.

DATA DELETION/DISPOSAL

Measures in this category pertain to the irreversible deletion and/or destruction of personal data so that it cannot be recovered. During data processing, the hosting system provided by the health partner does not use any local disk copies, nor any removable or portable devices to store the personal data.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	S.1	Software-based overwriting should be performed on all media prior to their disposal. In cases where this is not possible (CD's, DVD's, etc.) physical destruction should be performed.

PHYSICAL SECURITY

Physical security of the systems refers to measures designed to protect the systems hosting the SmartCHANGE solution and the managed data (e.g., server machines). This level of protection reduces the risk of direct—malicious and/or unauthorized—access by unauthorized personnel to these machines. The following measures are managed by the health partners.

Risk Level	Measure identifier	Measure description
L	T.1	The physical perimeter of the IT system infrastructure should not be accessible by non-authorized personnel.
M	T.2	Clear identification, through appropriate means e.g. ID Badges, for all personnel and visitors accessing the premises of the organization should be established, as appropriate.
M	T.3	Secure zones should be defined and be protected by appropriate entry controls. A physical logbook or electronic audit trail of all access should be securely maintained and monitored.
M	T.4	Intruder detection systems should be installed in all security zones.

M	T.5	Physical barriers should, where applicable, be built to prevent unauthorized physical access.
M	T.6	Vacant secure areas should be physically locked and periodically reviewed.
M	T.7	An automatic fire suppression system, closed control dedicated air conditioning system and uninterruptible power supply (UPS) should be implemented at the server room.
M	T.8	External party support service personnel should be granted restricted access to secure areas.

3.4.1 Mapping ENISA Requirements to MDCG Cybersecurity Guidance and AIA Requirements

In line with the precautionary analysis presented in Section 3.3 , this section provides a detailed mapping to demonstrate how the SmartCHANGE security framework aligns with potential regulatory obligations. The following cross-check table (Table 3) compares the project’s implemented security measures against the requirements of the Medical Device Coordination Group’s guidance (MDCG 2019-16[37]) and the key obligations of the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) [39].

The table organizes this compliance view using three main identifiers:

- **ENISA Measure:** References the security controls detailed in Section 3.4 of this document, identified by the format <SECTION_LETTER>.<NUMBER>. These are grouped using ENISA's macro-categories (e.g., Access Control, Logging).
- **MDCG Domain (D/N):** Corresponds to the domains from the MDCG guidance (i.e., Governance and Ecosystem; Protection; Defence; Resilience). This column uses a unique identifier in the format <DOMAIN_NUMBER>.<NUMBER>, where:
 - the DOMAIN_NUMBER indicates the domain to which the measure belongs.
 - the NUMBER represents the specific position of the measure within that domain.
- **AIA Requirement:** Directly references the relevant articles of the Artificial Intelligence Act that correspond to the security measure.

Both tags (i.e., DOMAIN_NUMBER and NUMBER) follow a numerical order.

Table 3 - ENISA requirements vs MCDG 2019-16 and AIA: a cross-check

D/N	MDCG Domain Name	ENISA Measures	AIA regulation
1.1	Information System Security Governance & Risk Management	Covered by the impact analysis in section 3.2.2	AIA article 9 (Risk management system)
1.2	Ecosystem Management	Covered by the security measures in section 3.4	
2.1	IT Security Architecture	Covered by the security measures in subsections <u>NETWORK/COMMUNICATION SECURITY</u> , Workstation security, Mobile/Portable devices	AIA Art. 15 (Cybersecurity, robustness)
2.2	IT Security Administration	Covered by the security measures in subsections Server/Database security, Data deletion/disposal	
2.3	Identity and access management	Covered by the security measures in subsections Access control and authentication, Mobile/Portable devices	AIA Art. 14 (Human Oversight)
2.4	IT security maintenance	Covered by the security measures in subsection Application lifecycle security	AIA Art. 15 (Lifecycle robustness)
2.5	Physical and environmental security	Covered by the security measures in subsection <u>PHYSICAL SECURITY</u>	
3.1	Detection	Covered by the security measures in subsections Logging and monitoring, Mobile/Portable devices	AIA Art. 12 (Traceability), Art. 15 (Resilience)
3.2	Computer security incident management	Covered by the security measures in subsections Back-ups, Logging and monitoring	AIA Art. 15 (Error handling)
4.1	Continuity of Operations	Covered by the security measures in subsection Back-ups	
4.2	Crisis Management	Covered by the security measures in section 3.4	

This unified mapping illustrates how the project's security posture is designed to satisfy the intersecting requirements of medical device cybersecurity and high-risk AI regulation.

3.5 Authentication and Authorization

In the SmartCHANGE platform, authentication and authorization are centrally managed through the OpenID Connect (OIDC) protocol, with the identity provider service based on Keycloak realizing the specification of the protocol. This configuration ensures a secure and standardized mechanism for managing user identities and granting access to system resources. When users log into the platform, Keycloak handles identity verification and issues access tokens that encapsulate the user's roles and permissions.

The platform defines four primary user roles:

- **Admin:** Manages users, roles, and system configurations across all services. Has full access to all data and administrative functionalities within the platform.
- **Practitioner:** Includes healthcare professionals (e.g., doctors, psychologists, therapists). Has access to full clinical data and risk prediction results. Can view and manage data only for patients within their own organization. Supports care planning, monitoring, and intervention management.
- **Teacher:** Has access to partial clinical information relevant to educational or behavioural interventions. Does not have access to sensitive clinical details or risk prediction results.
- **HappyPlant User:** Represents adolescent users and their families. Has access only to their own personal data, including assigned interventions and progress tracking.

These roles are consistently enforced across all integrated services within SmartCHANGE, enabling fine-grained control over functionalities and data visibility. Each service within the platform interprets user roles to tailor the interface and capabilities accordingly.

Beyond basic role-based access, SmartCHANGE leverages FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) authorization rules to regulate access to clinical resources at a granular level. These rules define what specific data each user can view, create, update, or delete, based on their role and the context of care. This ensures that patient privacy and data protection standards are upheld, while also supporting secure and efficient workflows for healthcare and educational professionals.

3.6 Data Privacy and protection

The SmartCHANGE project collects and processes a variety of personal and health-related data in compliance with GDPR applicable local laws and regulations. Each partner involved in this process has implemented tailored safeguards based on the type of data handled, institutional policies and local regulations.

From this perspective, each partner is responsible for ensuring compliance with data privacy and protection obligations at their respective sites. This includes the identification of a Data Protection Officer (DPO), the implementation of technical and organizational measures (e.g., ENISA), and securing the appropriate ethical approvals and Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) where required.

For all personal or sensitive data, the solution applies data minimisation, pseudonymisation, and when applicable, full anonymisation prior to storage or analysis. Data is only accessible to authorised personnel, stored in password-protected institutional or project repositories, and used strictly for the purposes defined in the Grant Agreement.

Notably, data reuse and sharing are restricted to protect individual privacy. To this end, sensitive datasets may only be shared under formal agreements established by each pilot study owner, who is responsible for applying these protective measures, and never in identifiable form. A detailed description of the implementation and such agreements is documented in the Data Management Plans (DMPs) within the WP7 and reported in the updated version of the deliverable D7.1¹⁰, while this document provides a high-level overview of the overall data privacy and protection framework.

¹⁰ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D7.1 – Study initiation package

4 Architecture Design

This section provides an overview of the system architecture, including a detailed description of the main components and their dependencies. The main interactions among them will be analysed in section 6.

The SmartCHANGE architecture, depicted in Figure 4, consists of multiple microservices, each exposing a well-defined set of APIs. The core system runs in a local platform, that will be deployed separately in each pilot site (see section 7 for details on deployment), while external clients such as the HCP Webapp or the mobile app services can interact through an HTTPS REST API managed by an API gateway. The API Gateway serves as the entry point for clients to interact with the backend services. The security of the external connections will be guaranteed by the usage of HTTPS and the OIDC based identity provider, which will provide single sign-on for all the clients and a role-based access to the services.

In relation to the core system, this is composed of several microservices, both SmartCHANGE specific and support services (identity management, metrics collection, and auditing). All microservices interact through REST APIs and rely on various repositories for storing data like identities, audits, state-information regarding the HappyPlant mobile app, and FHIR-compliant electronic medical records (EMR).

The AI framework is split into local and central subsystems. The local framework has components for data cleaning, visual explanation, federated learning, and risk prediction. These rely on repositories for model storage and local datasets. The federated learning setup includes both local (FLClient) and central (FLServer) components, allowing decentralized training on private data while leveraging public datasets for collaborative model improvement.

The principles that have driven the architecture design are modularity, with clear separation of concerns between microservices, scalability via the federated learning model, and privacy-preserving machine learning techniques. The use of REST APIs ensures interoperability between components, while the choice of FHIR-based clinical data storage ensures future interoperability with other (healthcare) systems.

In the next sections, each service will be described in more detail, and its interfaces and dependencies will be defined.

Figure 4 – Final SmartCHANGE solution component diagram.

4.1 Clients

SmartCHANGE solution includes a set of client applications that interact with the backend microservices. These clients serve different platforms and user roles, providing interfaces for accessing the system's functionality securely and efficiently. Each client is tailored to the needs of its target audience, through a comprehensive co-design process carried out in WP3.

The following sections provide an overview of the clients from a technical point of view, their intended use and their connection with backend services.

4.1.1 HCP Web Application

The HCP Web App is a browser accessible application developed in Angular used by Healthcare Practitioners, school teachers and administrators. It allows access to the risk predictions that give insights on the probability to develop certain diseases in the future and as well as the selection and customization of user-specific plan for lifestyle improvement with specific actionable goals. It also offers means to monitor the health status of children and adolescents, and the progress towards reaching the selected goals. The HCP Web App also offers functionalities to manage users and support the administrative processes needed for the pilot execution. The HCP Web App is deployed through a microservice that contains the Angular based application. Its container is used to serve static contents (e.g., HTML, JavaScript, images) to the client browser that can host the code and run it.

DEPENDENCIES

- **Clinical Repository**, to read and write clinical data from the children and adolescents
- The **XCDS Engine**, to retrieve the risk predictions from the AI services
- **Identity Provider** service, to provide authentication and authorization based on OIDC.

4.1.2 Mobile app for adolescents and families

The "HappyPlant" mobile application is currently being implemented as a cross-platform (Android and iOS) application used by children, families and adolescents for tracking and improving their lifestyle. After downloading the app from the official app store (Android currently available, iOS pending), users can choose which of the SmartCHANGE "Realms" to connect to (i.e. Slovenia, Portugal, the Netherlands, Finland, Taiwan, or the "Development Realm"). After having selected the realm, all further communication occurs only with that specific service instance of the SmartCHANGE back-end services. Specific user types,

registered in the **Identity Provider** as ‘patients’ can login to the application and have access only to their own data. A further distinction is made by tags – intervention group vs control group – that dictate the specific functionalities that the HappyPlant application provides. All users will have to provide some data by answering questionnaires that will be stored in the **Clinical Repository**. Both user types also can connect to a Garmin wearable device that tracks physical activity and sleep data. This connection is made ‘locally’ over Bluetooth through the app’s integration of the Garmin SDK. This data is split into two parts, where summarized daily values of certain parameters are provided in FHIR format to the **Clinical Repository** and the raw sensor data is stored, for future additional research in the **Garmin MongoDB Repository**. Users in the control group will from this point on only be able to visualize summarized data from the Garmin device, whereas the core HappyPlant features are provided for users in the intervention group only. The HappyPlant app will initially poll the **XCDSBroker** with requests for Initial Risk Predictions, that, after enough data is available to provide them, will kick-start the core HappyPlant behaviour change loop. In this loop, users can choose a “pet plant” to adopt and start earning water to keep the plant happy and make it grow, until it can be planted in the garden (see D3.7 and D3.8 for further design details). Information about the state of the plant, as well as other supporting services for the plant-challenge-water loop is supported by the **HappyPlant Service**, a back-end microservice used for storing plant state information and the challenge database and related services. The mobile app is a cross-platform (Android and iOS) application used by families and adolescents for tracking and improving their lifestyle. It makes use of data from the user’ wearable and communicates this data with the respective healthcare practitioners.

DEPENDENCIES

- **Identity-provider** service, to provide authentication and authorization based on OIDC.
- **Clinical Repository**, to read and write clinical data from the children and adolescents.
- **Garmin MongoDB Repository** provides API endpoints for dumping raw Garmin data for future analysis.
- **XCDSBroker**, a “broker” service that mediates between different services, used by HappyPlant to request risk prediction information.
- **HappyPlant Service** – service used for persisting HappyPlant state data, as well as for hosting the database of available challenges (including corresponding API endpoints).
- The **messaging** service, to allow exchanging chat messages with the HCPs using the webapp
- **Keycloak** service, to provide authentication and authorization based on OIDC

4.1.3 Visual Explainer

The counterfactual visual analytics tool, usually named Visual Explainer, is a web application developed using Svelte, which allows health practitioners to follow-up on explorative or investigative analysis of counterfactual cohort beyond what they can do with the HCP Web Application. Assuming a doctor uses the HCP Web Application and have follow up questions, they click a link within the HCP Web Application forwarding the examined prediction ID to the Visual Explainer. There, the doctor can investigate the subject's counterfactual cohort to better understand their situation and the various potential directions they could take. Though flexible, it is important to note that the Visual Explainer is not a tool which suggests plans of action for the subject or the doctor, but rather with the extra information seen through the visualizations, the doctor can make a more informed decision. The Visual Explainer is also aimed at providing the machine learning experts a glimpse of how their models interact with each other and to audit if the results are as expected, or if further development is needed for a given model. Additional information can be found in the D5.2¹¹ document.

SECURITY CONSIDERATIONS:

Calls to the SmartCHANGE platform backend are authenticated. User credentials are securely shared between the HCP Webapp and the VE through the user browser session Dependencies

The XCDS Engine, to retrieve data of the examined subject and the counterfactuals generated by the explainer.

4.2 SmartCHANGE Services

This section outlines the microservices that compose the SmartCHANGE solution. Each microservice is responsible for a specific capability, communicating with others through well-defined APIs. This architecture facilitates easier maintenance, parallel development, and scaling of individual components based on demand.

The following sections detail the various microservices that comprise the solution, their responsibilities, communication patterns, and dependencies. Each microservice is designed

¹¹ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D5.2 Initial trustworthy AI suite

to operate autonomously, offering well-defined APIs to interact with other components. Together, they work to deliver the core functionality of the system, ensuring high availability, reliability, and performance across the distributed architecture.

Section 4.3 will cover the backend services that are based on existing open-source solutions, which have been configured and tailored for use in the project. These open-source services can provide robust, scalable solutions while minimizing development effort, not being core to the project innovation goals, accelerating project timelines, and leveraging community-supported software.

4.2.1 Clinical Repository

The Clinical Repository service (based on FHIR repository) is the backbone of the solution as it is the tool enabling the integration of the elements of the system. Its main capabilities consist of managing the health and sensitive data of the subject. The service regulates read and write access to clinical data managed by the platform. It implements the HL7 FHIR standard [1]. This service is accessible by the other components of the system, which must be authorized in advance to perform operations on the data. The solution is designed to be modular, platform independent and compliant with the GDPR by applying the privacy-by-design approach. Given those guidelines the solution can be deployed to any cloud commercial solution as long as a specific Data Processing Agreement (DPA) is in place. The FHIR data server delegates control over the user's authorization to the Security manager module, which checks the user requesting read or write access to the database and allows (or prevents) their access.

Finally, the FHIR data server uses the services provided by the auditing service (see section 4.3.5) to track all data reading and writing operations and then store them into an immutable auditing database as to be further compliant with GDPR requirements.

INTERFACES

The service exposes an interface that can be accessed by clients through the HTTPS protocol. The main services that are supported can be summarized as:

- Read

- vRead¹²
- Create
- Delete
- Update
- Search
- Batch / Transaction

These operations comply with the HL7 / FHIR standard, described on the standard's website [43].

DEPENDENCIES

- **Keycloak** service, to provide authorization based on JWT tokens.
- **Postgres DB.** The Clinical Repository will use a relational database to store data. It leverages on a JDBC access protocol and therefore supports any DBMS that can be connected via that protocol. In particular, the prototype created for the purposes of the project uses a Postgres server, which provides adequate guarantees on the management of security in compliance with privacy requirements. In fact, Postgres allows the tracing of the operations carried out directly through the DBMS.

4.2.2 XCDS Engine

Within the SmartCHANGE solution, the role of the XCDS Engine is to act as a broker between the HCP Web App (the Client) and the services providing risk prediction and explanation (ML services). The broker is based on the CDS Hooks 2.0 specification [41], and extends some of the standard data structures to enrich the information that can be exchanged, including a richer description of the models and support the exchange of explanations to the outputs of the AI models. The data structures used and the extension to the standard is described in the interface section.

The XCDS Engine is responsible for retrieving all the necessary clinical data and forwarding it to the AI services. In particular, in the current architecture the Explainer service acts as the

¹² vRead (version Read) is a specific type of read operation in the FHIR standard that allows you to retrieve a **specific version** of a resource by its ID and version ID.

service that aggregates the information on both risk predictions and explanations. Details on the service are provided in section 4.2.3.2.

The service is designed to be flexible, so that new AI services can be added or modified without changing the client implementation. To do so, the XCDS Engine maintains a list of all available services providing decision support, their endpoints, supported hooks, and required prefetch templates.

Being responsible to prefetch the necessary clinical data ensures that the AI services have all the information needed to generate meaningful guidance or recommendations. Once the engine has pre-fetched the required data, it forwards the entire request, including both the original trigger information and the pre-fetched data, to the Explainer. The Explainer in turn processes the request and returns a response, as described in the corresponding section.

After receiving the response, the engine aggregates and formats the information as per the CDS Hooks standard before sending it back to the HCP Web App. In addition, the XCDS Engine is enabled to save the generated cards locally, making them available for later access. The HCP Web App can then present this information to the healthcare provider.

The usage as a broker and the compliance to a standard such as CDS Hooks provides a clean separation between the webapp and potentially multiple decision support services while also optimizing the flow of clinical data to provide timely and relevant decision support.

INTERFACES

Service Registry:

- **DESCRIPTION:** Get a description of all CDS services offered by this CDS Provider
- **PATH:** GET /cds-services
- **INPUT:** none
- **OUTPUT:** List of *XCDS*Service

Get Prediction

- **DESCRIPTION:** Send a request for a prediction
- **PATH:** POST /cds-services
- **INPUT:** *XCDS*ServiceRequest
- **OUTPUT:** List of *XCDS*Card

Get Explanations

- **DESCRIPTION:** Send a request to get additional counterfactuals given an existing prediction
- **PATH:** POST /counterfactuals
- **INPUT:** *prediction_id, counterfactual_configuration*
- **OUTPUT:** List of *CounterfactualsCounterfactual*

DEPENDENCIES

- The XCDS Engine depends on the **Explainer** service to provide risk predictions and explanations, conforming to the description provided in a XCDSservice instance.
- The XCDS also depends on a FHIR R5 compliant **Clinical Repository** to retrieve health data for the AI services.

4.2.3 Trustworthy AI service

The overall explainer service consists of a risk predictor, which forecasts disease risks, and an explainer, which shows how changes to a person's profile could help reduce those risks. Federated learning is also integrated to enable secure, privacy-preserving model training.

4.2.3.1 Risk Predictor

The Risk Predictor is a tool to predict the health risk of a person. It operates by analysing the variables describing the person's current health. The inputs to the Risk Predictor are some of the health variables that the machine learning and public risk models need. They are expected at ages between 6 and 14 (one age only). In case some of the inputs are not provided by the user, for example because the general practitioner does not have the necessary equipment at that moment or because the children cannot have their blood test at the moment of the visit, they are instead imputed from the remaining inputs - from those that the user did provide. The Risk Predictor then infers the values of additional variables required for the prediction: these are the variables that are useful for the analysis of risk but are never provided by the users (it is not practical to require that, for example, 30 different inputs/variables be measured for a child), such as the amount of triglycerides in blood. The Risk Predictor then forecasts the values of all variables at age 55, when non-communicable diseases become common.

It inputs the variables at the age indicated into one or more existing risk-prediction models. Specifically, it uses the SCORE2 [65] and Health Heart Score [66] models for cardiovascular disease (the first relying more on biological variables, the second on lifestyle), and the Test2Prevent model [67] for diabetes. In addition to the risk and health variables (risk factors)

at age 55, the Risk Predictor can also provide the same at lower ages, which can be used for plotting the evolution of risk (factors) over time. The detailed methodology of the Risk Predictor is described in D4.2¹³.

When the risk predictor service is called by HappyPlant, the model also returns a global risk score, which represents the overall risk derived from all three separate risk models and serves as a recommendation for whether to visit HCP. It's important to note that, for HappyPlant, we wait for 7 days to gather reliable measurements of physical activity, sleep, and calories burned, which are then used to calculate the risk.

While not yet implemented in the initial prototype, the Risk Predictor has the potential to incorporate federated learning for model training. The specific models involved may evolve as the risk prediction methodology is refined.

INTERFACES

The Risk Predictor is contained in the Explainer, since the Explainer already heavily depends on the Risk Predictor and constructing additional, separate module does not offer any advantages.

Predict risk

- **DESCRIPTION:** Invoke the service to get a risk prediction
- **INPUT:**
 - a list of key / value pairs representing the values of all relevant input data for the risk prediction. The actual list of keys is dependent on the type of prediction. Some values can be null; in this case the model will infer those values.
 - the disease it is predicting among a set (e.g. "DIABETES", "CVD")
- **OUTPUT:** a list of risk values, each composed of a pair <age, risk>.

DEPENDENCIES

The Risk Predictor does not call any further component.

¹³ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D4.2 Baseline prediction pipeline

4.2.3.2 Explainer

The Explainer module is designed to provide insights into the Risk Predictor's outputs by generating counterfactuals. These counterfactuals highlight the necessary modifications to a subject's profile that would alter their risk of developing a specific disease. In addition to enhancing interpretability, these counterfactuals can serve as actionable recommendations for doctors to propose to the participants. When implemented in real-life scenarios, these recommendations encourage healthier behaviours, ultimately reducing the risk of disease development.

Our Explainer module takes as input the individual's current condition, predicts the risk using the Risk Predictor, and utilizes the processed information, along with the target risk factor, to generate the counterfactuals. Moreover, it offers temporal flexibility: counterfactuals can be generated not only for the present moment but also for a future time frame (e.g., one year from now) to support long-term recommendations and goals for the individual.

The Explainer requires training, which can be carried out in a federated learning (FL) setting. There are two training approaches:

1. **Joint Training:** The Explainer and Risk Predictor are trained simultaneously. This approach allows the Explainer to influence the training process of the Risk Predictor, leading to potentially better integrated models.
2. **Post-Hoc Training:** The Risk Predictor is trained independently, and once its parameters are fixed (frozen), the Explainer is trained on top of it.

Both training approaches are compatible with federated learning (FL) scenarios. However, we are still evaluating which strategy will be most effective for our use case. At this moment, we opted for the Post-Hoc FL training, as it allows us to preserve the integrity of the pre-trained Risk Predictor while enabling the Explainer to adapt flexibly to each local dataset without interfering with the predictive model's original learning dynamics.

INTERFACES

When these functions are called, the service queries the Explainer which interacts directly with the Risk Predictor.

Predict and explain:

- **DESCRIPTION:** Invoke the service to get a risk prediction and the corresponding explanation

- **PATH:** POST /execute
- **INPUT:** ServiceInput: Includes the user data, how many counterfactuals to generate, the desired risk of the counterfactuals and the year of the subject for which we want to generate counterfactuals
- **OUTPUT:** ServiceOutput: The predicted risk and the generated counterfactuals and their risk

Explain:

- **DESCRIPTION:** Invoke the service to get the corresponding explanation of an already generated risk prediction
- **PATH:** POST /explain
- **INPUT:** *ExplanationRequest*
- **OUTPUT:** list of *XCDSEExplanation*: The generated counterfactuals

DEPENDENCIES

- Risk Predictor

4.2.3.3 FL Services

The FL Services component is responsible for enabling secure and efficient distributed learning across multiple machines or institutions. Its primary purpose is to facilitate the concurrent training (or fine-tuning) of a predictor and explainer model without transferring the clients' raw data to external servers, thereby ensuring data privacy and compliance with regulations such as the GDPR. The component establishes a client instance on each machine that owns the data, while the server coordinates the aggregation of locally computed updates. Secure protocols are employed to enhance robustness against adversarial contributions and minimize the risk of data leakage.

The key functionalities of this component include:

- **Model Initialization:** The server initializes the FL process by distributing the initial parameters of the pre-established models (i.e., predictor and explainer) to each client.
- **Client-Server Communication:** The component coordinates communication between the clients and the central server, with clients transmitting local updates and metrics to the server, and the server sharing global model parameters and aggregated results back to the clients, ensuring communication integrity and security.

- **Aggregation:** The server aggregates the local updates from all clients to generate a global model, which is then shared back with the clients for the next iteration of training.
- **Performance Monitoring and Adaptation:** The component continuously monitors the performance of the global model and adapts the learning process to improve accuracy, reduce overfitting or underfitting, and maintain model robustness.
- **Secure Aggregation:** The component might include additional privacy-enhancing technologies to further ensure data confidentiality and integrity.

INTERFACES

Invoke:

- **DESCRIPTION:** This interface is used to initiate the FL process, supporting both the post-hoc training of new models and the fine-tuning of pre-trained predictor and explainer models.
- **PATH:** POST /execute
- **INPUT:**
 - **Device role:** Indicates whether the container should act as a server or a client
 - **Target risk type:** Specifies the risk type to train the Explainer for (e.g., hhs, score2, be_kul)
- **OUTPUT:** The trained model parameters for both predictor and explainer

DEPENDENCIES

Dependencies from Other Components in SmartCHANGE

- **Current Model Parameters:** For fine-tuning, the location of the pre-trained models must be provided. When training from scratch, models are randomly initialized. **Note:** training the Explainer requires access to a pre-trained Predictor.
- **Client Dataset Locations:** Information on where the client datasets are stored, along with any necessary preprocessing steps.
- **Model Architectures:** Specifications of the predictor and explainer model architectures to be used in the training process.

Libraries

- **Preprocessing Libraries:** Required libraries for data preprocessing, if applicable.
- **Model Training Libraries:** Libraries used to create and train the predictor and explainer models.

- **Flower Library:** A federated learning library used to manage the FL process, coordinate client-server interactions, and perform model aggregation.

4.2.4 Data Cleaning Service

The Data Cleaning Service is designed to handle the preprocessing, cleaning, and harmonization of diverse datasets. The primary purpose of this component is to ensure that all datasets, regardless of their origin, are standardized and cleaned before being merged into a unified dataset that is used to train the models. Because of dataset restrictions and signed NDAs, all cleaning and harmonization happens offline, and the resulting dataset is shared only with authorized partners. The component addresses various data quality issues, including missing values, outliers, irrelevant data, duplicates, and harmonization issues. It offers flexible cleaning methods adaptive to the specific needs of the datasets and a harmonization process that aligns the data structure and format across all datasets to facilitate integration.

The key functionalities of this component include:

- **Data Preprocessing - Source-Specific Preprocessing:** Before the harmonization process is initiated, each dataset is subjected to source-specific preprocessing. Variables of interest are renamed to match the harmonized schema (which contains the list of variables, target formats, and derived measures with predefined formulas). Categorical values are recorded to match the unified coding system, and various unit conversions are applied to ensure consistency in scale.
- **Data Harmonization:** Datasets are reshaped to a common structure, then concatenated into a single table. Since different sources capture similar but not identical variables, semantic harmonization is also applied. Shuttle-run-speed is predicted using a formula that was adjusted to match the variables that our dataset had. To normalize values and enable comparisons across age and sex groups and to allow integration of data from cohorts using different measurement protocols and units, all relevant physical activity and fitness variables were transformed into age and sex specific z-scores. This standardization places each individual's values on a common scale relative to their peers and removes differences in measurement units across studies. Z-scores were computed for variables including moderate to vigorous physical activity, shuttle-run speed, the Andersen Test, VO₂ Max, the six minute walk test, and the 600-meter run. A similar harmonization strategy was applied to derive a socio-economic status (SES) indicator for each participant. Because SES was captured using different variables across cohorts, such as parental education, household income, employment status, and neighbourhood characteristics among others, these inputs were first semantically aligned as individual z-scores and then averaged to create a composite SES index. Three z-scores are computed, for physical activity and fitness, based on age and sex groups,

using moderate to vigorous physical activity, shuttle-run speed, and standing long jump. Finally, exact duplicates are identified and removed to produce a non-redundant, integrity-preserved harmonized dataset.

- **Data Cleaning and Imputation:** In this step outlier detection is happening. Specifically, any non-null entry is flagged as an outlier if it either takes a negative value (in cases where negativity is not theoretically valid) or deviates from the mean by more than five standard deviations ($|x - \mu| > 5\sigma$). Detected outliers are treated as structurally missing and recoded as NaN. Imputation is subsequently carried out using a k-nearest neighbours' algorithm, which belongs to a class of non-parametric, instance-based learning method, and missing values are estimated. An auxiliary binary flag matrix is generated in parallel, where each cell is coded as 1 if the corresponding value was imputed, and 0 if it was originally observed.

INTERFACES

Data Cleaning

- **DESCRIPTION:** This operation applies all the identified cleaning methods to the list of datasets, harmonizes them and downloads the cleaned and harmonized version of the dataset. Additionally, all the detailed log files documenting all changes made during the cleaning process is also downloaded.
- **INPUT:** -
- **OUTPUT:** *CleaningReport*: Returns the downloaded version of the dataset alongside the log files

DEPENDENCIES

The Data Cleaning Service has no external dependencies.

4.2.5 Data Anonymization Service

To ensure compliance with ethical and legal standards and protect participant identities, data to be collected through the feasibility study, given the sensitive nature of them, undergoes an anonymization procedure that maintains anonymity for the participants. All the feasibility study data to be collected, were categorized into 4 categories: (1) Identifiers: Directly reveal or strongly narrow to a single individual, (2) Quasi-Identifiers: Attributes that on their own will not identify someone but, when linked (even with external data) can be used to re-identify participants, (3) Sensitive Attributes: All medical/health conditions plus certain vital signs. Disclosure of these may cause harm/discrimination and is protected by privacy rules and (4) Non-Sensitive Attributes: General lifestyle or behaviour metrics, which do not uniquely identify a single individual. After the categorization of all the variables, the

anonymization process to be followed for each one was identified, given the options of total removal, generalization, noise addition, micro aggregation and bucketization.

INTERFACES

Anonymization Service

DESCRIPTION: This interface is used to initiate the anonymization process

PATH: POST /anonymization

INPUT: - Clinical data dataset

- Garmin wearable dataset {the set of these two datasets for each pilot}

OUTPUT: One anonymized version of the dataset, alongside with one non-anonymized version of the dataset

DEPENDENCIES

The Data Anonymization Service depends on the Clinical Repository service to get access to clinical data managed by the platform and the mobile app for adolescents and families

4.2.6 HappyPlant Back-End Service

The HappyPlant Back-End Service is an additional microservice that has been added to the architecture after the first technical specification provided in D6.1. After the start of the implementation process it became clear that additional data persistence (beyond the data that can be reasonably stored in the Clinical Data Repository) was necessary in order for the HappyPlant app to properly function.

The HappyPlant Back-End Service thus provides API endpoints to store any state information about the application that does not contain clinical data (or raw Garmin data, which is stored in its own separate micro-service). This state information can be broadly categorized in two parts: plant state, and challenges. For the plant state, end-points are available to get and set specified variables (e.g. `current-plant-name`). For the challenge related operations, two specific functions are provided by the service. The first is to get and set events related to challenge (e.g. `challenge-completed`). The second is the `get-suggestion` end-point that provides a list of tailored challenges from which the user can select which ones to accept for the coming week.

Interfaces

/happyplant/plant/update-state-variables – For a specific end-user (HappyPlant user), update a set of state variables related to the adopted plant (e.g. currently adopted plant name, current amount of water in watering can, current plant growth stage, list of completed plants).

- /happyplant/plant/get-state-variable – For a specific end-user, retrieve one or many state variables related to the plant-state.
- /happyplant/challenge/get-suggestion – For a specific end-user, retrieve a list of suggested challenges, tailored to the current user and time (based on data in the Clinical Repository).
- /happyplant/challenge/update-history – For a specific end-user, store a specific challenge-related event (e.g. challenge complete, challenge accepted, challenge revoked).
- /happyplant/challenge/get-history – For a specific end-user, retrieve a set of elements from the challenge history, filtered by type, start- and end-times.

Dependencies

- Identity-Provider – All calls to the HappyPlant Service are authenticated by the end-users JWT.
- Clinical Data Repository – In order to provide a tailored list of challenge suggestions, the service retrieves data from the clinical repository.

4.3 Services based on existing solutions

4.3.1 Wearable Device (Garmin)

The Garmin VivoSmart 5 fitness tracker was selected as the wearable of choice for this project because of its minimal design, low price, and the possibility to use the wearable without subscribing to any proprietary cloud service or third-party application.

Garmin offers a fully featured, out-of-the-box solution in their Garmin Connect API and cloud service. However, this project's target audience is too young to make use of the Garmin Connect cloud for storage and processing of data, it would not be compliant with Garmin's terms of service. Instead, the project uses the official Garmin Software Development Kit (SDK). The SDK is currently integrated with the native Android implementation of the application and be integrated with the IOS version of the app as well. This SDK takes care of the Bluetooth pairing and data synchronization with the wearable.

The wearable has local storage, where it can store up to 14 days' worth of tracked data. Upon synchronization, which should happen preferably each day, the HappyPlant mobile application receives the data from the wearable in Garmin's API format, at which point the wearable forgets the data. The mobile application extracts daily summaries of data and

translates this to be FHIR compliant before sending it to the Clinical Data Repository our API for processing and storage. Additionally, raw Garmin data is sent to the Garmin MongoDB Repository (part of the SmartCHANGE backend). At no point is any of the data that is collected by the wearable sent to Garmin, or indeed any other 3rd party.

4.3.2 API Gateway

In a microservices architecture, the client apps usually need to consume functionalities from more than one microservice. If that consumption is performed directly, the client needs to handle multiple calls to microservice endpoints. Therefore, having an intermediate level or tier of indirection (Gateway) can be convenient for microservice-based applications. The API-gateway is a service acting as the single-entry point into the system. It is similar to the Façade pattern from object-oriented design. It encapsulates the internal system architecture and provides an API that is tailored to each client. It also has other responsibilities such as authentication, load balancing, and static response handling. Moreover, it is responsible for request routing, composition, and protocol translation. All requests from clients first go through the API-gateway. It then routes requests to the appropriate microservice. The api-gateway will often handle a request by invoking multiple microservices and aggregating the results. It can translate between web protocols such as HTTP and WebSocket and web-unfriendly protocols that are used internally. Moreover, the API-gateway is also responsible of managing cross-cutting concerns such the management of SSL. The api-gateway is based on the open-source product **Traefik** - released with MIT license.[42]

4.3.3 Identity provider

The SmartCHANGE platform provides sign up and login functionality through **Keycloak**, an open-source Identity and Access Management solution that simplifies the process of securing applications and services. It supports standard protocols like OpenID Connect (OIDC), OAuth 2.0, and SAML 2.0, making it versatile for various authentication needs [16].

Keycloak provides features such as Single Sign-On (SSO), user federation, and fine-grained authorization, which streamline user management and enhance security. Its web-based admin console allows for easy configuration and management, reducing the complexity for developers. The centralization of authentication and authorization processes in Keycloak ensure a consistent and secure user experience across multiple applications. This makes Keycloak an ideal choice for organizations looking to improve security, reduce administrative overhead, and provide a seamless user experience.

In Figure 5, a schema illustrating how Keycloak works is reported. It acts as a central authentication server, managing user identities and access permissions. Applications and services (CLIENT side) delegate authentication to Keycloak, which verifies user credentials and issues tokens for access (SERVER side). This centralized approach not only simplifies the integration of security features but also ensures that all applications adhere to the same security standards, making Keycloak a robust and scalable solution for modern identity and access management.

Figure 5 - Keycloak: OIDC Authentication and Authorization flow.

4.3.4 Monitoring

Monitoring is the practice of tracking and analysing the operations and performance of individual microservices within a larger application architecture (as the SmartCHANGE platform). This involves gathering, reporting, and storing data (monitoring the API calls) to ensure each microservice is functioning correctly and efficiently and can interact with each other to deliver the expected results. In this way, monitoring provides a comprehensive view

of the application's key areas and performance during development, enabling targeted decisions in later phases. The monitoring component will be made of the following modules:

- A *call-tracing* module, based on the product **Zipkin** [44], which is released with an Apache License 2.0. In particular, the module enables the distributed tracing of the transaction by helping to gather timing data needed to troubleshoot latency problems in service architectures. Features include both the collection and lookup of this data. To be able to monitor all transactions within the solution, services of the whole platform are instrumented to notify it whenever a transaction is conducted.
- A *metrics-collector* module, acting as a probe for the collection and structuring of infrastructure monitoring data. This module will scrape metrics from instrumented applications, either directly or via an intermediary push gateway. This module is based on the open-source product **Prometheus**, released with *Apache License 2.0*. [57]
- A *monitoring dashboard*, offering the capability of defining custom charts and alerts by leveraging the information collected by the *metrics-collector* module. The dashboard is based on the open-source product **Grafana**, released with *Apache License 2.0*. [56]

4.3.5 Logging & Auditing

Log components are meant to centralize the container logs as to support log analyses. A log collector component, based on the lightweight **Grafana Loki** stack, provides support for logs collection and visualization. The service parses the containers logs as to extract structured data collector like timestamp, log level and message. Those data are then pushed to a *log aggregator*. The *log-aggregator* component is based on the open-source product **Loki** - released with *Apache License 2.0*. The logging components are customized with logs retention policies, according to the project needs. [55]

To prevent tampering, and enabling auditing, logs are stored in an **immudb** based repository. *immudb* is an open-source database with built-in cryptographic proof and verification. It can track changes in sensitive data and the integrity of the history are protected by the clients, without the need to trust the server repository.

5 Data Model

This section defines the types of data exchanged among services within the SmartCHANGE solution. It outlines the data categories, their sources, and the flow of information between system components. Additionally, the section discusses the role of each service in the data exchange process, ensuring that the interactions are aligned with security, privacy, and performance requirements.

5.1 Health data managed the SmartCHANGE Solution

5.1.1 Data collected by the SmartCHANGE clients

Health data managed by the SmartCHANGE Solution is collected by the two clients, the HCP Web App and the HappyPlant mobile app.

The mobile application primarily shares activity data measured by the wearable and qualitative data gathered via short questions questionnaires presented to the user. This data allows to calculate the user's future health risks and allows HCPs to monitor their young participants.

In addition, the mobile application *receives* some data from other system components:

- Initial and updated risk prediction, influencing the behaviour of the app.
- Goal adjustments by HCP.

The webapp for HCPs mainly consumes data stored in the Clinical Repository, to populate the health dashboards of the individuals in care with the HCPs, while it produces health data, that can be entered by HCPs during the encounters with the persons they have in care, through dedicated forms.

The webapp also produces *goal assignments* and *risk predictions* and provide a functionality to register the families and adolescents that use the SmartCHANGE solution, thus it produces registration information.

Table 4 gives an overview of the data collected by the clients, with an indication of the client responsible for collecting the specific information.

Table 4: Overview of collected data.

Category	Type	Webapp (User input)	Webapp Happy Plant (Wearable)	Happy Plant
Socio-demographic information	Age	x		
	Sex	x		
Physical and vital measurements	Weight	x		x
	Height	x		x
	Subjective Physical Activity			x
	Waist	x		
	BMI (derived from height and weight)	x		x
	Blood pressure (systolic and diastolic)	x		
	Heart rate	x		x
Daily Physical Activity (Wearable)	Minutes of moderate PA per day		x	x
	Minutes of vigorous PA per day		x	
	Steps per day		x	x
	Total calories per day		x	x
	Active calories per day		x	x
	Sleep hours / day		x	x
Basic dietary information	Servings of fruit/berries per day			x
	Servings of vegetables per /day			x
	Servings of nuts per day			x
	Servings of cereals per day			x
	Servings of sugary drinks per week/day			x
	Servings of red and processed meats per week/day			x
Screen Time	Hours of screen time per day			x
Lifestyle	Fitness test results	x		
	Smoking	x		
	Alcohol	x		
Socioeconomic	Family wealth (Socio-Economic Status) SES)			x
Blood tests	Cholesterol (Total, HDL, LDL)	x		
	Glucose (fasting glucose)	x		
	Blood pressure medication	x		
	Child diabetes diagnosis	x		
	Child CVD diagnosis	x		
	Family diabetes	x		
	Family CVD	x		

	Latent Diabetes	x		
Psychological	Psychosocial assessment questionnaire	x		

5.1.2 Risk Factors produced by the models

Within the Trustworthy AI Framework, the Risk Predictor forecasts the following variables, that are also used by the explainer to produce counterfactuals.

Table 5 Overview of risk factors produced by the AI models

Category	Risk factor
Physical and vital variables:	Height
	Weight
	Waist / Hip circumference
	BMI
	Blood pressure (systolic and diastolic)
	Resting heart rate
Blood biomarkers	Glucose (fasting glucose)
	Cholesterols (LDL, HDL, Total)
	Triglycerides
Diet	Healthy heart score diet score
	Test2Prevent diet score
Lifestyle factors	Sleep
	Smoking
	Alcohol
Physical activity and fitness level	Physical activity (z-score and hours/week)
	Fitness z-score

However, to support healthcare professionals in focusing on the most actionable factors, we estimate risk attribution using only a selected subset of variables: physical activity, fitness z-score, BMI, healthy heart score diet score, sleep, smoking and alcohol. This simplifies interpretation while keeping the focus on factors that are most relevant for clinical decision-making.

5.2 FHIR: the standard for clinical data

Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) [1] is a REST-ful based approach developed by HL7 for modelling data structures as Healthcare Resources and services as REST-APIs to provide a solution for **health interoperability**. This ensures that healthcare information can

be exchanged and integrated seamlessly, securely, and efficiently across different systems and organizations. Some key aspects are discussed here below.

INTEROPERABILITY:

- **Simplified Implementation:** FHIR aims to simplify the implementation process without sacrificing information integrity. It leverages existing logical and theoretical models to provide a consistent and easy-to-implement mechanism for exchanging data between healthcare applications.
- **Modular Components:** FHIR uses modular components called “resources” to represent different types of healthcare data, such as patients, observations, medications, and procedures. These resources can be combined in various ways to meet different healthcare needs, enhancing flexibility and scalability.
- **Semantic Interoperability:** FHIR addresses semantic interoperability by standardizing the terminology used within healthcare systems. This is achieved through FHIR Profile Resources, which define the specific health terminologies (e.g., SNOMED-CT [2], ICD [4], LOINC [3]) used by different adopters. By mapping these terminologies, different systems can understand and use the data consistently.

DATA EXCHANGE:

- **Standardized Formats:** FHIR supports multiple data formats, including JSON, XML, and RDF, making it versatile for different systems and applications. This standardization ensures that data can be easily exchanged and understood across different platforms
- **RESTful API:** FHIR uses RESTful APIs, which are widely adopted in web services, to facilitate efficient and secure data exchange. This approach allows for seamless communication between systems, enabling real-time data sharing and integration.

SECURITY AND PROVENANCE:

- **Robust Security Protocols:** While FHIR itself is not a security protocol, it defines exchange protocols and content models that need to be used with various security protocols. This includes the use of TLS for secure communications, OAuth for authentication, and a security label infrastructure for access control.
- **Audit and Provenance:** FHIR includes resources for tracking the origins, authorship, history, status, and access of data, ensuring transparency and accountability.

5.2.1 Usage of FHIR standard in SmartCHANGE

Building upon the above discussion, here below some details on the FHIR R5 resources that were used to model the data gathered by the mobile app, the wearables and the web app in the SmartCHANGE project.

5.2.1.1 FHIR resources used in the project

1. **Patient** is a foundational element that represents key demographic and administrative information about an individual receiving care. This includes data such as name, age, gender, contact information, and other personal identifiers. The Patient resource **is central to almost all healthcare interactions in FHIR**, serving as a link between the individual and the various health records, observations, assessments, and treatments that pertain to them.[7]
In the SmartCHANGE project this resource has been used to map key demographic information, such as the individual's sex and age, which are critical for context when interpreting other health data. These demographic factors are often essential for tailoring health assessments, risk predictions, and treatment plans to the individual's specific needs. In addition, the individual's country has been included in the mapping to support a feature - in the Explainer's input data – that determines risk region category based on geographic location.
2. **Related Person** represents Information about a person that is involved in an individual's health or the care for a subject, but who is not the target of healthcare. In SmartCHANGE, the family members will be modelled with both the Patient resource, as they may be the subject of some activities in the behaviour change strategies, and through the use of the RelatedPerson resource, to represent their relationship with the mail subject of care. The strategy used is the one described in [60].
3. **Practitioner** represents an individual who is involved in the delivery of healthcare services. This can include various healthcare professionals such as **doctors, nurses**, pharmacists, therapists, and other clinical or **non-clinical personnel** who contribute to subject care. The resource captures essential information about the practitioner, including their qualifications, certifications, specialties, and contact details. It serves as a critical component for documenting who is responsible for delivering specific aspects of care and linking that information to individual health records.[10] The specific roles or functions (e.g., general practitioner, specialist, IT specialist) a Practitioner may hold within an organization or healthcare setting is defined by the **PractitionerRole**. This resource links a Practitioner to his/her responsibilities, location, services provided, and the healthcare organization he/she is associated with. PractitionerRole is particularly useful for managing complex healthcare settings where professionals may fulfil multiple roles across different contexts or organizations.[11] In the **context of the SmartCHANGE project**, these resources were used to map both clinical and non-clinical experts: the school nurse, the general practitioner (GP), and the AI expert. In particular, the Practitioner resource captured essential details about their

qualifications, certifications, and contact information ensuring that each professional's identity and expertise were documented, regardless of their specific role or specialization. By utilizing the PractitionerRole resource, the system effectively highlighted the distinct responsibilities and areas of expertise that each professional brought to their respective fields:

- a. the school nurse's role was defined within the educational setting, focusing on adolescent health, first aid, and health screenings, and linking him/her to the school where he/she worked.
 - b. the general practitioner's role was tailored to providing primary care for children aged 6-10, with a focus on paediatric care, routine check-ups, immunizations, and growth monitoring, usually in association with a clinic or hospital.
 - c. the AI expert's role, while non-clinical, was pivotal in healthcare innovation, specifically in developing and applying ML and AI algorithms for risk prediction of cardiovascular and metabolic diseases. This role emphasized his/her contribution to data analysis, model development, and collaboration with clinical professionals, defining his/her unique position within the healthcare framework.
4. **RiskAssessment** is used to **evaluate and document the likelihood of a particular outcome or condition occurring, based on specific factors or risk indicators**. This resource typically includes the risk prediction, the factors contributing to this assessment, and any recommendations or interventions that might mitigate the risk. RiskAssessment is crucial for preventive care, as it helps in identifying individuals who may benefit from early interventions or monitoring to prevent the development of serious conditions.[6]

In the SmartCHANGE project this resource has been used to assess and document the likelihood that a person will develop cardiovascular or metabolic diseases in adulthood. This risk is calculated based on data collected through both web and mobile applications, encompassing lifestyle factors, medical history, physical measurements, and other relevant health indicators. The RiskAssessment provides a predictive model that can inform both participants and healthcare providers about potential future health risks, allowing for early intervention or lifestyle modifications.

5. **Goal** captures specific health objectives or targets set for the subject, often based on clinical assessments or risk predictions. It reflected measurable challenges, such as managing disease risk or improving health outcomes, and is used to guide treatment plans and individual care strategies over time[53]. A **CarePlan** describes the intention of how a practitioner intend to deliver care for a particular individual for a period of time. They may describe education campaigns [58].
6. **Observation** is designed to capture and represent measurements, assertions, and assessments regarding an individual's health status. This resource is highly versatile and can represent a wide variety of clinical and non-clinical observations, including **vital signs**, laboratory results, **physical measurements**, and even **lifestyle indicators** such as physical activity or dietary habits. The Observation resource is essential for documenting the subject's condition over time, enabling clinicians to track changes and trends in health-related data.[5]

In the SmartCHANGE project this resource has been used to map various types of health-related data, including:

- *Physical and Vital Measurements*, capturing metrics like heart rate, blood pressure, height, weight, etc.
- *Blood Biomarkers*, recording laboratory results such as glucose levels, cholesterol, etc
- *Lifestyle Behavior*, monitoring lifestyle choices like smoking, and exercise habits.
- *Physical Fitness*, tracking fitness levels through measurements such as BMI, body fat percentage, or performance on fitness tests.

7. **Questionnaire** is designed to define structured sets of questions intended for data collection. These questions can range from simple yes/no formats to more complex input types, such as multiple-choice or free-text answers.[8] **Questionnaire Response** captures the actual responses provided by participants or healthcare providers. Together, **these resources facilitate the collection of structured information, which can then be analysed, stored, or converted into other relevant FHIR resources.**[9]

In the SmartCHANGE project these resources have been used to capture initial individual information through structured surveys. These questionnaires might gather data on medical history, lifestyle habits, symptoms, or general health concerns. The responses provided were then stored as QuestionnaireResponse resources and were used directly for analysis or converted into other FHIR resources, such as Observations, when the information was linked to measurable health data.

8. **Organization** represents entities involved in the provision of healthcare services, such as hospitals, clinics, and other healthcare facilities, including details about the organization's name, type, contact information, address, and the services provided.[51]

In the SmartCHANGE solution this resource has been used to map the healthcare structures where participant had encounters or was under care, contributing to the coordination of care across different healthcare entities.

9. **Encounter** captures interactions between a subject and healthcare provider for the purpose of providing healthcare services. This resource includes information about the type and reason for the appointment, the date and time of the encounter, and the involved participants. By documenting the specifics of each healthcare interaction, the Encounter resource facilitates better coordination of care and a clearer understanding of the individual's healthcare journey.[54]

In the SmartCHANGE project this resource has been used to map details of healthcare interactions, such as the type and reason for the appointment, or instances when the healthcare provider or school nurse interacted with the subject. This setup facilitated the systematic gathering and organization of user data throughout the care process.

10. **NutritionIntake** details the dietary intake of a participant, including types and amounts of food and drink consumed. This resource also captures information on the individual's nutritional habits and any related observations, supporting nutritional assessments and interventions.[52]

In the SmartCHANGE project this resource has been used to map the subject’s dietary habits, including their consumption of food and beverages, as well as alcohol consumption. By documenting these details, the NutritionIntake resource provides valuable insights into the young participant’s nutritional status and potential health risks.

11. **ServiceRequest** represents a request for a procedure, diagnostic test, or other service to be performed for a patient. It includes a wide range of actions such as diagnostic tests, specialist consultations, **counselling**, therapies, and other clinical interventions. [59].

In the SmartCHANGE project this resource has been used to manage targeted interventions (i.e., “Counselling prescription”) based on the outcome of a risk evaluation. This information is provided by the supportingInfo field that is a crucial reference back to the **RiskAssessment** (see point 4) that generated the suggestion.

Appendix 1 reports the details of the FHIR Data model and how the health data produced in the SmartCHANGE solution (and described in the previous sections) will be persisted.¹⁴ The same data model is used to send the relevant clinical data to the AI services, and to obtain a risk assessment value, thus it is crucial in guiding the development phase.

¹⁴ The mappings of project data to specific FHIR resources and terminologies (i.e., codes) were managed in a specific Excel file (‘data-inputs-to-fhir.xlsx’). It serves as the operational source of truth for development and is accessible to project members with the appropriate credentials.

6 Data Information Flow

This section includes diagrams that depict the interactions among system components, users, and external systems. The flows are described using UML Sequence Diagrams and describe the main interactions between the platform services that support the scenarios described in D6.7.

6.1 User creation

6.1.1 HealthCare Practitioner

6.1.2 HappyPlant user (PU)

6.2 HappyPlant: Download, Install, Initial Questionnaire

6.3 Initial risk assessment and decision to involve an HCP

6.4 HCP meets with PU (and family) and evaluates risk

6.5 HCP sets goals for a PU

6.6 HappyPlant: PU Starts First Week of Challenges

6.7 HCP opens and uses the Visual Explainer tool

6.8 Federated Learning

6.8.1 Federated Learning initialization

Figure 6: FL initialization

6.8.2 Federated Learning model training

Figure 7: Federated Learning

6.9 Data Cleaning

6.10 Creation of anonymized dataset from SmartCHANGE clinical data

7 Deployment and testing

The Final Integration and Test Plan (D6.7¹⁵) establishes a comprehensive framework for software development, integration, and testing within the SmartCHANGE project. This plan introduces a three-tiered environment strategy, encompassing Development, Test, and Production stages, to ensure stability and integrity throughout the development lifecycle. More in details:

- **Development Environment** - This is where developers create and test code. It's a flexible environment for experimentation and debugging.
- **Test Environment** - This environment replicates the production environment as closely as possible, allowing for rigorous testing of the application under realistic conditions.
- **Production Environment** - This is the live environment where the application is deployed for end-users. It should be highly stable and secure.

Central to this approach is the mandated use of Docker [47] as a popular platform for containerization, which involves packaging applications and their dependencies into a single unit (a container) that can be run consistently across different environments. This has several advantages:

- **Portability:** Containers can be easily moved between different machines and environments.
- **Consistency:** The same container behaves the same way regardless of the underlying infrastructure.
- **Efficiency:** Containers are lightweight and start up quickly.

In the SmartCHANGE project, using Docker for containerizing microservices facilitates consistent deployment across various environments and pilot sites, reducing the risk of compatibility issues. A schematic representation of the approach is schematically presented in Figure 8.

¹⁵ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D6.6 Initial Integration and Test Plan

Figure 8 - Development to deployment cycle, based on continuous feedback and improvement.

For effective code management, the plan adopts GitHub [49] as the central code repository and container registry, implementing a specific branching strategy aligned with the project's environmental structure. By using GitHub as the central code repository, the followings are ensured:

- **Track changes** - Every change to the code is recorded, making it easy to revert to previous versions if necessary.
- **Collaborate** - Multiple developers can work on the same project simultaneously.
- **Manage issues** - Bugs and feature requests can be tracked and assigned to specific developers.

Moreover, to support uniform deployment across pilot sites, Deliverable 6.6¹⁶ provides a detailed blueprint for virtual machine configuration capable of running the containerized microservices. Additionally, API documentation is streamlined through the implementation of Swagger [48], generating interactive and up-to-date documentation that enhances communication and accessibility for all stakeholders. The plan also outlines a comprehensive testing strategy spanning different environments, coupled with a structured bug reporting system utilizing GitHub's issue tracking features.

In Figure 9, it becomes visible that for each user in a different pilot site, their data is saved and processed on a server owned by the respective pilot site.

¹⁶ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D6.6 Initial Integration and Test Plan

Moreover, in D6.6¹⁷ an integration roadmap that outlines a phased approach for component integration, progressing from stub implementation to final system delivery is also presented. This ensures a smooth transition from development to production stages. Collectively, these elements form a robust framework for managing the technical aspects of the SmartCHANGE project, promoting efficient development, seamless integration, and reliable deployment of the project’s software components.

Ultimately, in order to support the 2-phase pilot plan, the deployment strategy - here broadly reported - will also undergo 2 cycles. Hence, the contents of D6.6 will have a final version that is planned to be released at month 24 were updated in D6.7, released at M24.

Figure 9 – Final Deployment diagram showing the interaction of one mobile application with the pilot locations, where data is saved.

¹⁷ SmartCHANGE Consortium. Deliverable D6.6 Initial Integration and Test Plan

8 Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable marks the final version of the technical specification for Work Package 6 (WP6) of the SmartCHANGE project. It consolidates the technical vision, system architecture, and data strategy into a robust and deployable platform, reflecting the maturity achieved since the initial specification (D6.1) at M18. The refinements presented here are grounded in real-world feedback from pilot testing, cross-WP integration efforts, and adaptations to evolving regulatory and technological landscapes.

Throughout the project, SmartCHANGE has maintained its commitment to a user-centred and privacy-first design. The solution now comprises two fully specified tools: a mobile app for families, children, and adolescents; and a web-based application for HCPs. Together, these tools support personalized, proactive management of NCD risk through trustworthy, explainable, and secure AI technologies.

Key advances since D6.1 include the consolidation of AI components into a unified Trustworthy AI Framework, the integration of backend support for data-rich functionalities (such as the HappyPlant app and Garmin data ingestion), and the introduction of a Data Anonymizer service that enables compliant reuse of clinical data from pilot studies. The data model has also been finalized with FHIR-based mapping, ensuring interoperability with healthcare systems and adherence to established standards.

The architecture continues to follow a microservices paradigm, promoting scalability, flexibility, and maintainability across all components. This architecture supports secure and modular development, enabling individual services to evolve independently while maintaining system integrity. Additionally, technical and organizational safeguards have been enhanced to reflect the latest GDPR-compliant privacy measures, especially in the context of federated learning and decentralized AI training.

This deliverable also provides updated technical definitions for service interactions, APIs, communication protocols, and data flows, fully aligned with the new functionalities and usage scenarios identified in WP3. The deployment and testing strategies presented in Chapter 7 further ensure that SmartCHANGE is prepared for real-world implementation and scaling beyond the pilot phase.

Looking ahead, while this marks the final deliverable for WP6, the technical foundations described here offer a clear roadmap for ongoing enhancement, evaluation, and broader adoption, towards the final SmartCHANGE solution, to be released in D6.4 - Midterm

SmartCHANGE solution prototype (due at m29). The project team will continue to monitor user feedback, system performance, and policy developments to inform any future iterations. SmartCHANGE now stands as a mature, trustworthy, and user-aligned digital health solution, ready to support healthier lives through innovation, personalization, and secure AI.

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Appendix 1. Data model to HL7-FHIR R5 mapping rules and terminologies

The appendix document lists three types of tables, each addressing a different aspect of the profile:

The **FHIR Resources** section details how general concepts managed by the SmartCHANGE platform are mapped in FHIR resources, detailing which of the optional fields were used and any constraints specific to the project. The following sections detail the actual codes and conventions used to map the concepts consistently, for each type of resource used.

A1.I. FHIR Resources

The tables in this section are structured as follows:

- the *Data to Collect* column lists the data collected within the SmartCHANGE solution.
- the *FHIR Resource* column specifies the name of the FHIR resource (e.g., *Patient*, *Questionnaire*, *NutritionIntake*) to which the data collected is mapped.
 - This column is further broken down into sub-columns that indicate the specific fields within the selected FHIR resource that are populated during the mapping process.
- the *FHIR Note* column, when present, provides additional information.

SUBJECT (FHIR PATIENT)

	Patient FHIR	
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Data to collect	field	Type (FHIR datatype)	Valueset	Note
age	birthDate	Date [01/MM/YYYY]		to support a feature - in the Explainer's input data – that determines risk region category based on geographic location.
gender	gender	code	Administrative Gender Valueset	
pilot	address.country	3-letter ISO code of Country		

FAMILY HISTORY (FHIR QUESTIONNAIRE)

Family History

<http://it4h.eng.it/uhm/Questionnaire/prevention-patient-health-history>

Questionnaire FHIR							
Data to collect	questionID	required	repeats	answer type	valueset	enable when	text
Child CVD diagnosis	diagnosed_cvd	false	false	boolean			Is the child currently diagnosed with CVD?
Blood pressure medication	hypertension_drugs	false	false	boolean			Was the child ever taking blood pressure medication on a regular basis?
Child diabetes diagnosis	diagnosed_diabetes	false	false	boolean			Is the child currently diagnosed with diabetes?
High Glucose	latent_diabetes	false	false	boolean		diagnosed_diabetes = false	Was the child ever found to have elevated blood glucose (e.g., during a health examination, during an illness ...)
Diabetes Type	diagnosed_diabetes_type	false	false	code	Diabetes Valueset	diagnosed_diabetes = true	Which type of diabetes was the child diagnosed with?

Family diabetes	diabetes_family_history_members	false	true	code	Family History Valueset	Does any member of the child's family have diabetes?
Family CVD	cvd_family_history_members	false	true	code	Family History Valueset	Does any member of the child's immediate family, such as a parent or sibling, have a heart attack or a stroke, or was diagnosed with heart disease before the age of 60?

LIFESTYLE (FHIR QUESTIONNAIRE)

Lifestyle

<http://it4h.eng.it/uhm/Questionnaire/prevention-patient-lifestyle>

Questionnaire FHIR							
Data to collect	questionID	required	repeats	answer type	valueset	enable when	text
Fitness test results	20-m-srt-laps	false	false	number			20m Shuttle Run Test. How many laps did you complete?
Fitness test date	20-m-srt-date	false	false	date			When was the test taken?
Self-reported Fitness Level	self-fit-status	false	false	boolean	Answer Rating Score Valueset		What do you think about your physical fitness? It is ...
Smoking	smoking-status	false	false	code	Smoking Status Valueset		Do you currently smoke?
Alcohol	alcohol-consumption	false	true	code	Nutrition Servings Valueset		How many servings of alcohol per week do you consume (number/prefer not to say)?

NUTRITION SERVINGS (FHIR NUTRITIONINTAKE)

Nutrition Servings to NutritionIntake FHIR mapping

Data to collect	consumedItem.type.coding	consumedItem.nutritionProduct.coding	consumedItem.amount
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	system	code	display	system	code	display	value	unit	code	system
Fruit	http://snomed.info/sc †	255620007	Food (substance)	http://snomed.info/sct	72511004	Fruit (substance)	integer	/day	/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Vegetable	http://snomed.info/sc †	255620008	Food (substance)	http://snomed.info/sct	22836000	Vegetable (substance)	Integer	/day	/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Nuts and seeds	http://snomed.info/sc †	255620009	Food (substance)	http://snomed.info/sct	13577000	Nut (substance)	Integer	/day	/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Sugary Drinks	http://snomed.info/sc †	226465004	Drinks (substance)	http://snomed.info/sct	818989004	Sugar sweetened beverage (substance)	Integer	/week	/wk	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Meat	http://snomed.info/sc †	255620009	Food (substance)	http://snomed.info/sct	28647000	Meat (substance)	Integer	/week	/wk	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Cereal Grain	http://snomed.info/sc †	255620010	Food (substance)	http://snomed.info/sct	23182003	Cereal Grain (substance)	integer	/day	/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org

MEASURES (FHIR OBSERVATION)

Observations to Observation FHIR mapping						
Data to collect			Observation FHIR			
Patient			subject			
Recording date			effectiveDateTime			
Reference to patient or HCP			performer			
Status of the observation (is always set to 'final')			status			
	code		value.valueQuantity			
	system	code	value	unit	code	system
Weight	http://loinc.org	29463-7	number	kg	cm	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Height	http://loinc.org	8302-2	number	cm	cm	http://unitsofmeasure.org

Minutes of moderate PA per day/week	http://loinc.org	77592-4	number	min/day	min/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Minutes of vigorous PA per day/week	http://loinc.org	77593-2	number	min/day	min/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Steps per day/week	http://loinc.org	41950-7	number	number/day	{#}/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Total calories per day/week	http://loinc.org	41981-2	number	kcal/day	kcal/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Active calories per day/week	http://loinc.org	93819-1	number	kcal/day	kcal/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Sleep hours / day (mobile app)	http://loinc.org	93832-4	number	hour/day	h/d	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Waist	http://snomed.info/sct	276361009	number	cm	cm	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Total cholesterol	http://loinc.org	14647-2	number	mmol/L	mmol/L	http://unitsofmeasure.org
HDL	http://loinc.org	14646-4	number	mmol/L	mmol/L	http://unitsofmeasure.org
LDL	http://loinc.org	22748-8	number	mmol/L	mmol/L	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Fasting Glucose	http://loinc.org	76629-5	number	mmol/L	mmol/L	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Resting Heart Rate	http://snomed.info/sct	444981005	number	beats/minute	/min	http://unitsofmeasure.org
BMI	http://loinc.org	39156-5	number	kg/m2	kg/m2	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Blood pressure	http://loinc.org	35094-2	Has components (Observation.component)			
	component.code		component.valueQuantity			
	system	code	value	unit	code	system
Systolic BP (as components di Blood Pressure)	http://loinc.org	8480-6	number	mmHg	mm[Hg]	http://unitsofmeasure.org
Diastolic BP (as components di Blood Pressure)	http://loinc.org	8462-4	number	mmHg	mm[Hg]	http://unitsofmeasure.org

CAREPLAN (FHIR CAREPLAN)

Careplan to Careplan FHIR mapping								
Data to collect	Careplan FHIR							
	category		goal	period		status	created	intent
	system	code		start	end			
Sleep	http://snomed.info/sct	247950007	array of Goal Reference (see GOAL mapping table)			active cancelled		plan
Physical Activity	http://loinc.org	77242-6		date	date		dateTime	
Nutrition	http://loinc.org	77243-4						
Default plan	http://snomed.info/sct	385991005						

GOAL (FHIR GOAL)

Goal to Goal FHIR mapping														
Data to collect (textual description)	Goal FHIR													
	description		lifecycle Status	target					target2					
	system	code		measure		detail[x]		due[x]	measure		detail[x]		due [x]	
				system	code		default(s)	unit		system	code		default(s)	unit
						detail.range			due.dueDuration			detail.range		

Sleep between {MINIMUM} and {MAXIMUM} hours per night, each day of the week.	http://loinc.org	93833-4	proposed accepted	http://loinc.org	93833-4	range	12-ago	hours	1d								
						detail.detail Quantity						detail.detail Quantity					
						value	comparator					value	comparator				
Reach {VARIABLE} number of steps on every day of the week.	http://loinc.org	41950-7	proposed accepted	http://loinc.org	41950-7		>=	5000		1d							

Eat at least {VARIABLE-1} portions of fruit and {VARIABLE-2} portions of vegetables per day.	http://smartchange.eu	5- portions-a-day		http://snomed.info/sct	72511004				1d	http://snomed.info/sct	22836000					1d
						>=	2						>=	3		
accumulate XX min of vigorous activity per day	http://loinc.org	77593-2		http://loinc.org	77593-2				1d							
						>=	30	min								
accumulate XX min of moderate activity per day	http://loinc.org	77592-4		http://loinc.org	77592-4				1d							
						>=	60	min								
drink water	http://smartchange.eu	no-ssb		http://snomed.info/sct	818989004				1d							
						<=	0									

instead of Sugary drinks																	
do not use screens after XX PM	http://smartchange.eu	no-screen		http://smartchange.eu	switch-off-at					1d							
Through physical activity, burn at least {VARIABLE} calories every day of the week.	http://loinc.org	93819-1		http://loinc.org	93819-1		<=	21		1d							
This week, exercise at least {VARIABLE-1} times for at least {VARIABLE}	http://smartchange.eu	exercise-frequency		http://smartchange.eu	exercise-sessions		>=	200	kc al	1w	http://smartchange.eu	exercise-duration		>=	30	min	1 session
							>=	3									

BLE-2} minute s each session .																		
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CONSULTATION (FHIR SERVICEREQUEST)

Consultation to ServiceRequest FHIR mapping											
Data to collect	Careplan FHIR										
Info from the suggestion card	code		category		supportingInfo	status	priority	intent	subject	authoredOn	
	system	code	system	code							
		http://snomed.info/sct	6061000124109	http://snomed.info/sct	409063005	Risk Assessment reference (from suggestion card)	active revoked	routine urgent	proposal	Patient reference	dateTime

A1.II. FHIR Valuesets for SmartCHANGE

In the following section are reported the codes of used the project's data model from standard clinical vocabularies - i.e. LOINC (<http://loinc.org/>) and SNOMED CT (<http://snomed.info/sct>) - select international edition), and specifically for the project (<http://smartchange.eu/fhir/ValueSet/{id-for-the-specific-valueset}>) and the units of measure from the international unit of measure - i.e. UCUM (<http://unitsofmeasure.org>).

- The column Type, when present, is the name in the context of the valueset
- the System, Code and Display columns correspond to the coding from the one of standard vocabularies

Observation Valueset		
display	system	code
Weight	http://loinc.org	29463-7
Height	http://loinc.org	8302-2
Minutes of moderate PA per day/week	http://loinc.org	77592-4
Minutes of vigorous PA per day/week	http://loinc.org	77593-2
Steps per day/week	http://loinc.org	41950-7
Total calories per day/week	http://loinc.org	41981-2
Active calories per day/week	http://loinc.org	93819-1
Sleep hours / day (mobile app)	http://loinc.org	93832-4
Waist	http://snomed.info/sct	276361009
Blood pressure	http://loinc.org	35094-2
Systolic BP (as components di Blood Pressure)	http://loinc.org	8480-6
Diastolic BP (as components di Blood Pressure)	http://loinc.org	8462-4
Total cholesterol	http://loinc.org	14647-2
HDL	http://loinc.org	14646-4

LDL	http://loinc.org	22748-8
Fasting Glucose	http://loinc.org	76629-5
Resting Heart Rate	http://snomed.info/sct	444981005
BMI	http://loinc.org	39156-5

NutritionIntake Valueset

Type	system	code	display
Fruit		72511004	Fruit (substance)
Vegetable		22836000	Vegetable (substance)
Nuts and seeds		13577000	Nut (substance)
Sugary Drinks	http://snomed.info/sct	818989004	Sugar sweetened beverage (substance)
Meat		28647000	Meat (substance)
Cereal Grain		23182003	Cereal Grain (substance)
Food		255620009	Food (substance)
Drinks		226465004	Drinks (substance)

Unit Of Measure

Type	system	unit	code
Weight	http://unitsofmeasure.org	kg	cm
Height		cm	cm
Minutes of moderate PA per day/week		min/day	min/d
Minutes of vigorous PA per day/week		min/day	min/d
Steps per day/week		number/day	{#}/d
Total calories per day/week		kcal/day	kcal/d

Active calories per day/week		kcal/day	kcal/d
Sleep hours / day (mobile app)		hour/day	h/d
Waist		cm	cm
Blood pressure		No value. Has Components (Systolic and Diastolic)	
Systolic BP (as components di Blood Pressure)	http://unitsofmeasure.org	mmHg	mm[Hg]
Diastolic BP (as components di Blood Pressure)		mmHg	mm[Hg]
Total cholesterol		mmol/L	mmol/L
HDL		mmol/L	mmol/L
LDL		mmol/L	mmol/L
Fasting Glucose		mmol/L	mmol/L
Resting Heart Rate		beats/minute	/min
BMI		kg/m2	kg/m2
Fruit		/day	/d
Vegetable		/day	/d
Nuts and seeds		/day	/d
Sugary Drinks		/week	/wk
Meat		/week	/wk
Cereal Grain		/day	/d

Family History Valueset

<http://smartchange.eu/fhir/ValueSet/family-history-relationships>

system	code	display
http://terminology.hl7.org/CodeSystem/v3-RoleCode	GRPRN	Grandparent
	AUNT	Aunt
	UNCLE	Uncle

COUSN	Cousin
PRN	Parent
SIB	Sibling
OWNCHILD	Own Child

Diabetes Valueset

<http://smartchange.eu/fhir/ValueSet/diabetes-types>

system	code	display
http://loinc.org	94531-1	Type 1 diabetes mellitus
	94532-9	Type 2 diabetes mellitus
	94533-7	Gestational diabetes mellitus
	94533-7	Other specified diabetes mellitus

Smoking Status Valueset

<http://smartchange.eu/fhir/ValueSet/smoking-status>

system	code	display
http://snomed.info/sct	8392000	Non-smoker (finding)
	8517006	Ex-smoker (finding)
	77176002	Smoker (finding)
	373066001	Declined to answer

Nutrition Servings Valueset

<http://smartchange.eu/fhir/ValueSet/nutrition-questionnaire-servings>

system	code	display
http://smartchange.eu/fhir/CodeSystem/nutrition-servings	never	Never
	less-than-once	Less than once a week
	1	Once a week
	2	2 per week
	3	3 per week
	4-or-more	4 or more per week

Administrative Gender Valueset

Valueset-administrative-gender - FHIR v5.0.0

system	code	display
http://hl7.org/fhir/ValueSet/administrative-gender	male	Male
	female	Female
	other	Other
	unknown	Unknown

Answer Rating Score Valueset

<http://smartchange.eu/fhir/ValueSet/answer-rating-score>

system	code	display
http://loinc.org	LA9206-9	Excellent
	LA8967-7	Good
	LA8968-5	Fair
	LA8969-3	Poor

